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Systematic Review

Exploring the Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media for Organizational Engagement in SMEs: A Comprehensive Systematic Review

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Abstract: Social media platforms have become pivotal tools for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), offering vast opportunities for enhanced organizational engagement. However, these platforms also present challenges such as data privacy concerns, feedback management, and content saturation. This systematic review critically evaluates the existing literature on the dual role of social media in fostering organizational engagement while addressing key barriers faced by SMEs. We systematically assessed 104 peer-reviewed articles sourced from Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar, focusing on the impact of social media on marketing strategies and organizational outcomes in SMEs. The Newcastle-Ottawa Scale was used for quality assessment, and effect measures, including mean difference and odds ratio, were employed to evaluate performance metrics such as customer engagement, business performance, and long-term organizational impact. Key findings indicate that 74% of SMEs reported improvements in brand visibility, with customer engagement increasing by 65%. However, significant concerns were identified, with 45% of studies highlighting privacy issues and 52% addressing challenges in managing negative feedback. The review emphasizes that while social media can enhance market reach and customer interaction, its effectiveness largely depends on strategic content management and planning. This review provides actionable insights for SMEs aiming to optimize social media use, highlighting the need for future research to address privacy management and feedback strategies for sustained success.

Keywords: social media strategies; SMEs; organizational engagement; digital transformation; customer engagement; data privacy; systematic review

1. Introduction

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in economic growth, by innovation and entrepreneurship, social cohesion, and a foundation for large firms. However, they face several obstacles in the organizational engagement. In this age of digital communication that continues to expand timely, social media has emerged as a pivotal tool for organizational engagement for SMEs. It offers unprecedented opportunities to connect with audiences, enhance brand visibility, and foster customer relationships through platforms like Facebook, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Twitter [1]. The rapid growth of digital platforms has not only transformed traditional methods of communication but also revolutionized how organizations interact with their customers. For SMEs, which often operate with limited resources, social media provides a cost-effective avenue to compete on a global scale, build meaningful relationships, and maintain a consistent presence in the market. The global adoption of social media among SMEs has seen significant growth, with recent statistics indicating that 90.1% of SMEs are now utilizing social media for marketing and customer engagement purposes [62]. This widespread adoption underscores the relevance of examining how social media is impacting organizational engagement in practice. While some scholars emphasize the strategic benefits of these platforms highlighting how they foster authentic, dynamic communication channels

and help SMEs engage with larger audiences [4], others raise concerns about the ethical and operational pitfalls associated with data privacy, algorithmic control, and the potential for online backlash [5]. Diverging hypotheses in the literature focus on whether social media provides long-term benefits or whether it introduces unsustainable business risks for SMEs.

This review aims to critically analyze the existing literature, providing a balanced assessment of both the advantages and challenges that social media presents for SMEs. By synthesizing key publications, it will highlight strategic insights into the effective use of social media for engagement while addressing significant concerns related to privacy, negative feedback, and information overload [2,3]. Furthermore, this review aims to inform both academics and practitioners, offering evidence-based insights that could guide future research and provide practical recommendations for SMEs looking to optimize their social media strategies. Table 1 outlines the gaps in existing research, by showing the respective opportunities and disadvantages in the study based on use of social media in SMEs for organizational engagement.

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of the Existing Review Works and Proposed Systematic Review Challenges and Opportunities of Social Media for SMEs Organizational Engagement.

Ref.	Year	Contribution	Pros	Cons
[15]	2014	Analyzes public reactions to nonprofit messages on Facebook.	Identifies effective engagement strategies.	Focuses on nonprofit sector only.
[18]	2014	Studies adoption and use of social media in SMEs.	Cost-effective tool for customer engagement.	Requires persistent use for tangible benefits.
[14]	2015	Models' employee engagement using social media text analysis.	Provides real-time insights into engagement.	May not capture all engagement nuances.
[17]	2015	Examines social media use and its impact on corporate reputation.	Improves corporate reputation through consumer engagement.	Difficult to manage online conversations.
[19]	2015	Develops frameworks for strategic social media engagement to motivate directed actions.	Aligns social media activities with organizational goals.	Requires significant strategic planning.
[20]	2016	Examines CSR engagement via social media in theory and practice.	Integrates CSR with marketing communications.	Contextual factors may limit effectiveness.
[10]	2017	Analyzes employee social media engagement and the influence of power and social stake.	Enhances understanding of employee engagement dynamics.	Potential privacy concerns and misuse of power.
[13]	2017	Investigates dialogic strategies on Twitter for engagement.	Promotes interactive and synergistic communication.	Requires consistent and strategic content management.
[16]	2017	Investigates value co-creation through social media posts in cause brand communities.	Enhances community engagement and value creation.	Limited to specific case studies.
[30]	2018	Provides a systematic review of digital marketing and social media in SMEs	Comprehensive insights into digital strategies	Variability in adoption and effectiveness
[38]	2018	Reviews social media marketing's role in SMEs' sustainability	Long-term strategic benefits	Sustainability integration challenges

[29]	2019	Discusses opportunities and challenges for SMEs using social media in developing economies	Access to broader markets and cost-effective marketing	Infrastructure limitations and cybersecurity risks
[32]	2019	Analyzes social media marketing adoption in SMEs across different countries	Comparative insights and best practices	Cultural and regulatory differences
[34]	2019	Investigates multi-level impact of social media engagement on SME performance	Holistic view of engagement effects	Complexity in measuring multi-level impacts
[37]	2019	Explores opportunities and challenges of social media for SMEs in the digital age	Enhanced digital presence and competitive edge	Rapid technological changes and privacy concerns
[40]	2019	Examines the relationship between social media and innovation in SMEs	Encourages innovative practices and collaboration	Difficulty in measuring innovation outcomes
[24]	2019	Examines social media opportunities and challenges for SME engagement.	Enhances customer engagement and brand loyalty.	Risk of negative feedback and reputation damage.
[27]	2020	Examines how social media enhances business efficiency	Increased customer engagement and brand visibility	Potential for negative feedback and time-consuming management
[28]	2020	Explores social media use in SMEs in developing markets	Enhanced market reach and customer interaction	Limited resources and digital literacy challenges
[33]	2020	Reviews literature on social media's impact on SME performance	Identifies key performance drivers	Gaps in empirical evidence and methodological issues
[35]	2020	Identifies key success factors for SMEs using social media	Strategic insights for effective use	Challenges in implementation and resource allocation
[39]	2020	Empirical study on social media as a marketing tool for SMEs	Practical insights and data-driven strategies	Variability in effectiveness across sectors
[23]	2020	Explores intra-organizational challenges of online customer co-creation for innovation.	Facilitates innovation through customer collaboration.	Organizational resistance and resource allocation issues.
[31]	2021	Analyzes social media strategies for SMEs during crises like COVID-19	Adaptive strategies and crisis communication	Increased pressure on resources and rapid adaptation needs
[36]	2021	Examines challenges and opportunities in SME social media marketing strategies	Innovative marketing approaches	Resource constraints and evolving platforms
[22]	2021	Analyzes social media marketing in business interaction systems.	Enhances business communication and customer interaction.	Requires continuous monitoring and adaptation.
[26]	2021	Assesses regional innovation levels in Poland from 2010 to 2020.	Highlights regional disparities and innovation trends.	Limited to regional context and specific timeframe.

[11]	2022	Explores digitalization opportunities and challenges for SMEs.	Improved efficiency and market reach.	High costs and skill requirements.
[25]	2023	Discusses effective social media marketing strategies for overcoming challenges and maximizing opportunities.	Provides comprehensive strategies for modern business environments.	Requires adaptation to rapidly changing social media trends.
[12]	2024	Examines benefits, challenges, and drivers of open user innovation in low R&D SMEs.	Encourages innovation through external collaboration.	Implementation barriers and resource constraints.
[21]	2024	Studies social media's impact on entrepreneurship in Bangladesh, focusing on Pathao.	Enhance communication, marketing, and customer service.	Content saturation and digital literacy challenges.
		Proposed literature review	Covers both challenges and opportunities of social media for SMEs for organizational engagement, looking into both developed and developing countries, and offers insights on how social media can enhance brand loyalty, the privacy concerns it raises, and the KPIs	

The identified gaps in the literature reveal several critical areas that the proposed systematic review will address. Existing studies often focus narrowly on specific sectors or regional markets, limiting their applicability to SMEs across diverse industries and geographic contexts. Furthermore, while many works highlight social media's impact on customer interaction, there is a lack of comprehensive examination into key performance indicators (KPIs) such as ROI, brand loyalty, and customer trust, which are crucial for measuring long-term success. Additionally, challenges such as resource constraints, digital literacy, and privacy concerns are often noted but not adequately addressed with actionable strategies for SMEs. Another gap lies in the limited exploration of how recent algorithm changes on social media platforms affect SME engagement strategies. Finally, the current literature lacks a thorough investigation into the long-term effects of social media strategies on SME performance, with most studies focusing only on short-term gains. This review aims to fill these gaps by providing a holistic analysis of both the challenges and opportunities social media presents for SMEs, offering practical insights to optimize engagement strategies and sustain long-term success.

1.1. Research Questions

Despite a significant body of research on the use of social media for SME organizational engagement, a systematic review that comprehensively examines the relative challenges and opportunities remains underrepresented in the literature. This work aims to bridge this gap by systematically examining the available literature on social media's role in SME organizational engagement. To achieve this, the following research questions are explored:

- **RQ1:** How can organizations utilize social media strategies to enhance brand loyalty among existing customers?
- **RQ2:** What strategies are most effective for organizations in mitigating the impact of negative feedback on social media?

- **RQ3:** How do privacy concerns influence customer trust and engagement on social media platforms?
- **RQ4:** How have recent algorithm changes on social media platforms affected organic reach and engagement strategies for organizations?
- **RQ5:** What key performance indicators (KPIs) are most reliable for measuring the return on investment (ROI) of social media engagement in SMEs?

1.2. Rationale

The rapid proliferation of social media has significantly transformed the way organizations engage with their audiences. This shift presents both immense opportunities and notable challenges. As businesses increasingly rely on digital platforms to connect with customers and foster brand loyalty, it is essential to understand the full scope of social media's impact. This study is particularly timely in exploring how SMEs can capitalize on social media while navigating its inherent challenges, such as managing feedback, privacy issues, and evolving platform algorithms. Given the dynamic nature of these digital environments, staying informed on their developments is crucial for ensuring effective and strategic engagement. This review aims to provide valuable insights that will inform decision-making processes and improve the integration of social media into organizational strategies for SMEs.

1.3. Objectives

The objectives of this study are centered around examining how SMEs can leverage social media strategies to enhance customer engagement, manage negative feedback, and respond to privacy concerns, while also assessing the return on investment (ROI) of these efforts. The research is framed by the following goals:

- To investigate how organizations can use social media strategies to enhance brand loyalty among existing customers.
- To explore effective strategies for mitigating the impact of negative feedback on social media.
- To analyze how recent algorithm changes have affected organic reach and engagement strategies for organizations.
- To examine the influence of privacy concerns on customer trust and engagement on social media platforms.
- To identify reliable key performance indicators (KPIs) for measuring the return on investment (ROI) of social media engagement in SMEs.

Table 2. The Entailed Objectives and their Correlation to the Proposed Research Questions.

Objectives	Correlation to RQs
To investigate how social media strategies enhance brand loyalty among existing customers.	RQ1
To explore strategies for mitigating negative feedback on social media.	RQ2
To analyze the impact of recent social media algorithm changes on organic reach and engagement strategies.	RQ4
To examine privacy concerns and their influence on customer trust and engagement.	RQ3
To identify KPIs for measuring ROI of social media engagement in SMEs.	RQ5

1.4. Research Contribution

This systematic review synthesizes existing literature on how social media influences organizational engagement, providing a comprehensive overview of both the opportunities and challenges SMEs face. Previous research has often addressed individual aspects of social media engagement; this review consolidates these elements, offering a balanced perspective on social media's dual impact. The findings highlight the strategic benefits of improved customer engagement and brand awareness while critically addressing issues such as privacy concerns, information overload, and the effective management of negative feedback. This review provides valuable insights for both scholars and practitioners by offering a nuanced understanding of social media's role in SME organizational engagement. Additionally, it cautions against an overly optimistic view of social media, acknowledging the risks and contextual nuances involved in its use.

1.5. Research Novelty

This study contributes to the body of knowledge by offering a focused examination of social media's role in SME organizational engagement, filling a gap in existing literature that predominantly centers on large enterprises. By concentrating on SMEs, this review provides detailed insights into how these organizations can overcome resource limitations while maximizing customer engagement through strategic social media use. Furthermore, the study explores external factors influencing SME social media strategies, such as consumer behavior changes, platform regulations, and emerging digital trends.

The manuscript is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the literature on social media's impact on SMEs, outlining key opportunities and challenges. Section 3 details the systematic review methodology employed in this study, including the search strategy, eligibility criteria, and data analysis techniques. Section 4 presents the findings of the review, addressing the identified research questions. Section 5 discusses the implications of the findings for SME organizational engagement strategies and highlights areas for future research. Finally, Section 6 concludes the study, summarizing the key takeaways and offering strategic recommendations for practitioners.

2. Materials and Methods

This section outlines the systematic approach undertaken to analyze the challenges and opportunities of social media for SMEs' organizational engagement. The study spans a 10-year period, focusing on publications from 2014 to 2024. Based on a thorough review of the literature, it appears that no other studies have provided a comprehensive analysis of this topic within this timeframe. Figure 1 outlines steps/sections that were followed towards the completion of this systematic review. The methodology comprises guidelines for selecting studies, data origins, and the method utilized to review the collected literature laying the groundwork for an in-depth examination of each aspect in these sections. Figure 1 outlines a summary of sections in this systematic review

Figure 1. Summary of procedure followed in this Systematic Review.

2.1. Eligibility Criteria

A systematic review of all accessible, peer-reviewed papers related to social media's impact on SMEs' organizational engagement was conducted. The search targeted English-language publications from 2014 to 2024. This period is due to the rapid evolution of social media platforms and digital marketing strategies over the past decade, which have significantly influenced organizational engagement practices in SMEs. Earlier studies were excluded to ensure that the review reflects the most current and relevant insights, considering recent advancements in social media technology and usage patterns. The inclusion criteria focused on research that directly explores the opportunities and challenges associated with social media engagement in SMEs. Specific frameworks, such as models of digital marketing impact, customer engagement strategies, and organizational communication theories, were deemed acceptable. Articles that incorporated these frameworks and provided a deep analysis of social media's role in SMEs' organizational engagement were included. Studies that did not meet these criteria were excluded from the analysis. Table 3 summarizes the inclusion and exclusion criteria for this study.

Table 3. The Proposed Eligibility Criteria, Composed of Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

Criteria	Inclusion	Exclusion
Topic	Articles focusing on the challenges and opportunities of social media on organizational engagement in SMEs	Articles that do not specifically address the challenges and opportunities of social media on organizational engagement
Research framework	Articles that include frameworks such as digital marketing impact models, customer engagement strategies, and organizational communication theories	Articles that lack a focus on the impact of social media and digital marketing on business practices and customer engagement
Language	Articles published in English	Articles published in any language that is not in English
Publication Period	Publications between 2014 and 2024	Publications outside the 2014–2024 period

The timeframe of a decade period (2014-2024) was chosen due to significant developments in social media technology and strategies within the last decade. It captures the evolution of platforms like Instagram, LinkedIn, and newer features on platforms like Facebook and Twitter that have redefined organizational engagement. The study focused on articles that employed specific frameworks such as digital marketing impact models, customer engagement strategies, and organizational communication theories. This specificity ensured a targeted analysis of social media's strategic impact on SMEs.

2.2. Information Sources

For this systematic review, three primary databases were utilized: SCOPUS, Google Scholar, and Web of Science. These databases were selected for their extensive coverage of peer-reviewed literature and their multidisciplinary scope, ensuring a comprehensive retrieval of relevant studies. The search process involved using a combination of keywords and phrases pertinent to the study's focus on social media and organizational engagement in SMEs. These sources were accessed through well-established academic databases, including Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar. Each source was carefully selected based on predefined inclusion criteria to maintain the quality and reliability of the review, also Figure 2 outlines information sources steps in this systematic review.

- **Web of Science:** A multidisciplinary database providing access to a vast collection of high-quality, peer-reviewed research articles, conference proceedings, and book chapters across various fields, known for its citation tracking and analysis tools.

- Scopus: A comprehensive abstract and citation database covering a wide range of disciplines, including science, technology, medicine, social sciences, and arts and humanities, offering detailed citation metrics and high-quality research content.
- Google Scholar: A freely accessible search engine indexing scholarly literature from a diverse array of sources, including journal articles, theses, books, conference papers, and patents, providing broad coverage and accessibility to research materials.

Figure 2. Information Sources Flowchart for Retrieved Studies.

2.3. Search Strategy

The search process involved using a combination of keywords and phrases pertinent to the study's focus on social media and organizational engagement in SMEs, Table 4 outlines the keywords combination used.

Table 4. The Proposed Search Terms for Literature.

Search Terms
"Social Media" OR "Online Platform," OR "Digital Media,"
"Organizational Engagement" OR "Company Engagement" OR "Business Interaction," OR "Customer Engagement"
"Opportunities" OR "Benefits" OR "Advantages"
"Challenges" OR "Barriers," OR "Disadvantages"
"SMEs" OR "Small and Medium-sized Enterprises," OR "Small Business"

Using all the search terms supplied on table 4, a typical search string code applied in the databases was: ("Social Media" OR "Online Platform" OR "Digital Media") AND ("Organizational Engagement" OR "Company Engagement" OR "Business Interaction") AND ("Opportunities" OR "Benefits" OR "Advantages") AND ("Challenges" OR "Barriers" OR "Disadvantages") AND ("SMEs" OR "Small and Medium-sized Enterprises" OR "Small Business"). The total number of results from the initial search from each database is summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. Results Obtained from the Literature Search.

No.	Online Depository	Number of papers retrieved
1	Google Scholar	1150
2	Web of Science	48
3	Scopus	77
Total		1676

This search strategy was tailored and applied for each database, adapting and expanding the search terms based on the specific features of each, such as Boolean operators and filters. The process involved reviewing titles, abstracts, and keywords to identify studies that met the eligibility criteria. A broad range of materials, including journal articles, conference papers, book chapters, dissertations, and theses, was considered to ensure a diverse pool of relevant research.

To select the most needed or wanted research papers, a search process that was motivated by [6] and [7] was used and followed step-by-step for efficiency. The following diagram demonstrates the

steps used to categorize the research papers that are related to the opportunities and challenges of social media for SMEs Organizational Engagement:

Following the above steps from Figure 3, from the three online databases, we choose research papers related to our study were conducted as the first step. Secondly, the published papers that focused on the Opportunities and Challenges of Social Media for SMEs Organizational Engagement were selected and those which were not related to our study were excluded after being examined. Each reference list was checked for any extra citations that might point to new research papers and they were gathered. In the last step, When the search process reached the infiltration stage, where no more additional research could be found, the culling process began. The list of research papers that were chosen was cleaned and checked to check their relevance to the study. The steps used for this filtration are as follows: In the first step, the research titles were checked and scanned to see if they were relevant, and the abstract of the research papers and contents were also scanned to see if the content was important. The research papers were examined and reviewed again based on these criteria: they had to be published in English and include relevant frameworks to this study. The selected research papers had to be papers on similar topics from the last 10 years.

Figure 3. Search Strategy Selection Process.

2.4. Selection Process

This systematic review involves a subtle selection process to define which scholarly papers meet the eligibility criteria outlined in the previous section (2.1). This precise procedure is vital for guaranteeing the veracity and relevance of the literature included in the review. The selection process evolves in numerous steps, starting with identifying potentially eligible papers with a broad search strategy that employs a targeted wordlist. At the outset, the titles and abstracts of the papers are screened to eradicate unrelated papers. Then full-text critiques are carried out to evaluate the eligibility of the residual papers in better detail. It is pivotal to record the number of papers identified, screened, and included in the review, preferably portrayed in a PRISMA flow diagram, this diagram summarizes the selection process and details the reasons for exclusions at each stage. To improve the dependability of the resulting papers, several reviewers partake in the screening process, with each record being independently assessed by at least two reviewers, minimizing potential bias. Any clashes from the screened papers among reviewers are resolved through certain agreement or by consulting the alternate reviewer or AI, assuring a lucid decision-making process. The incorporation of automation tools has considerably simplified the selection process, aiding first screening by removing duplicates and prioritizing records based on predefined criteria. For example, software like Microsoft Excel 2016 assists in structuring records efficiently. Detailed documentation of the selection

methods is crucial for distinctness, including the number of records screened, excluded studies, and the rationale for exclusion, such as ineligible research frameworks. Furthermore, only papers presented in English were considered, enforcing the exclusion of any abstracts or papers written in any other language. This level of detail not only amplifies the credibility of the review but also gives a structure for future researchers to duplicate the procedure. Henceforth, a systematic review of this nature requires an organized approach to study selection, involving independent reviewers, the use of automation tools, and thorough documentation of the methodologies used.

2.5. Data Collection Process

A systematic data collection procedure was implemented to maintain precision. Three reviewers (T.M, R.E and M.N) independently gathered the data, while the fourth reviewer (B.A.T) validated the process to minimize errors and biases. Any disagreements were addressed through discussion until a consensus was reached among the reviewers. In cases where concerns about the data persisted, the fourth reviewer, an expert in the field, was consulted to review, verify, and ensure the reliability of the data interpretation. Feedback from the expert reviewer was provided to the first reviewer when inconsistencies were identified. The search for research papers was conducted across three different online databases, and when multiple reports from the same study were encountered, a comprehensive inclusion criterion, outlined in Table 4, was followed. This ensured the selection of recent, highly relevant data, and only papers written in English were included to minimize data bias and avoid potential misinterpretations that may arise from translation processes. Figure 4 illustrates the steps involved in the data selection and extraction processes.

Figure 4. Data Selection Process.

2.6. Data Items

In this Systematic Literature Review, the focus is on gathering information that explores the challenges and opportunities of social media for SMEs' organizational engagement. The outcomes are categorized based on research questions to provide a comprehensive understanding of the subject. This section of study outlines the methods used for Data Items.

2.6.1. Data Collection Method

In this systematic literature review (SLR), data was identified, analyzed, and assessed to ensure it met the rigorous inclusion criteria outlined in the previous section. The review concentrated on data pertinent to key social media metrics, including engagement, conversion rates, ROI and KPIs, and sentiment analysis. These metrics were examined over a decade-long publication timeframe, spanning from 2014 to 2024. Studies included in the review were required to provide sensible data on these metrics and demonstrate clear relevance to social media activities within SMEs. Priority was given to high-quality research studies that closely linked social media performance to SME outcomes, ensuring the inclusion of the most applicable data. Initially, the review focused on metrics such as subscriber or follower growth and brand awareness, both of which contribute to the strategic success of SMEs. However, metrics like engagement, reach, impressions, click-through rates, conversion metrics, ROI, and sentiment analysis were found to align more directly with the review's objective,

particularly in relation to SME strategic success. Figure 5 illustrates the step-by-step process followed in selecting relevant studies from the dataset.

Figure 5. Methodology of Data Collection Items.

2.6.2. Collected Data Variables Definition

Data was gathered from the specific online depository mentioned in the research studies, which included details such as the study title, year of publication, online databases, journal names, research types, industry contexts, geographical locations, economic contexts, types of social media platforms, social media metrics, applicable technology providers, technology implementation models, research designs, types of studies, sample sizes, sample characteristics, methods of data collection, data analysis techniques, social media performance metrics, business performance metrics, organizational outcomes, and long-term impacts. A summary of these variables is also available on an Excel spreadsheet compiled for this systematic review. The economic context in this review examines the type of countries where social media metrics investments in SMEs either existed or were lacking, helping to uncover the factors that influence SMEs' ability to meet organizational and long-term objectives, particularly regarding financial investments. In instances where some studies lacked specific details about social media platforms or industry context for SMEs, educated assumptions were made based on patterns observed in other published studies or case studies. This allowed for associating certain social media metrics with specific studies, and unspecified industries were presumed to be relevant in similar industry contexts. Table 6 outlines all the selected fields and their respective descriptions, and examples of data found in the fields

Table 6. Data Fields Collected from Literature Searches.

Fields	Description	Selections
Title	The title of the research article or paper.	None
Year	The publication year of the study.	None
Online Database	The database where the article was sourced.	Google Scholar, SCOPUS, Web of Science
Journal Name	The journal where the study was published.	None
Research Type	The type of research publication.	Article Journal, Conference Paper, Book Chapter, Dissertation, Thesis
Cites	The number of citations the article has received.	None
Discipline or Subject Area	The subject area the research focuses on.	Social Media, SME Engagement, Organizational Behavior
Industry Context	The industry or sector the research is focused on.	SMEs, Startups, Small Businesses

Geographic Location	The region or country where the study was conducted or focused.	None
Economic Context	The economic environment of the study.	Developed Countries, Developing Countries
Types of Social Media Platforms	The specific social media platforms used in the study.	Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, Instagram
Opportunities of Social Media	The opportunities that social media offers SMEs.	Brand Awareness, Customer Engagement, Market Reach
Challenges of Social Media	The challenges of using social media for SMEs.	Privacy Concerns, Resource Allocation, Content Management
Technology Providers	Companies or platforms providing technology for social media management.	Hootsuite, Buffer
Technology Implementation Model	The model of technology deployment, if applicable.	None
Research Design	The research design used in the study.	Experimental, Quasi-Experimental, Case Study, Survey
Type of Study	The type of methodology used in the study.	Quantitative, Qualitative, Mixed Methods
Sample Size	The number of participants or entities involved in the study.	None
Sample Characteristics	Characteristics of the sample in the study (e.g., SME owners, marketing managers, social media specialists).	SMEs, Marketing Managers, Social Media Specialists
Data Collection Methods	The methods used to gather data.	Interviews, Surveys, Observations, Document Analysis
Data Analysis Techniques	The techniques used to analyze the data.	Statistical Analysis, Thematic Analysis
Social Media Performance Metrics	The metrics used to evaluate social media performance.	Engagement Rate, Follower Growth, Conversion Rate
Organizational Outcomes	The outcomes related to organizational performance.	Employee Satisfaction, Customer Satisfaction
Long-term Impacts	The long-term impacts of social media use on SMEs.	Business Sustainability, Competitive Advantage

2.7. Study Risk of Bias Assessment

One of the most important tools for assessing the quality of nonrandomized research which includes group and case-control studies is the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale. The selection of study groups, group comparability, and outcome or exposure evaluation are its three main areas of concentration. For certain criteria within these areas, each assessment is assigned a star rating where a rating of nine stars indicates a lesser degree of bias. Comparison, which deals with how comparable the groups are with respect to important confusing factors such as Outcome/Exposure, which deals with defining the outcomes in group studies or identifying exposures in case-control studies; and Selection, which evaluates the evaluation process by using the NOS for the selection of study groups and representatives. It is considered to have a Low Risk of Bias for studies that have accrued 7-9 stars, Moderate Risk of Bias for 4-6 stars and High Risk of Bias for 0-3 stars based on the total in these categories. Each study was reviewed independently by two reviewers with any disagreements resolved by discussion and a third reviewer if required. On the other hand, it is important to underline that no automation tool was used, considering the risk of bias. Table 7 illustrates the structure of Newcastle-Ottawa Scale table for assessing the risk of bias in the studies [119–133].

Table 7. Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for Assessing the Risk of Bias in Studies.

Paper ID	Study Type	Selection (Max 4 stars)	Comparability (Max 2 stars)	Outcome/Exposure (Max 3 stars)	Total Stars	Risk of Bias
[REF X1]	X	★★★★	★★	★★	8	Low
[REF X2]	X	★★★	★★	★	6	Moderate

[REF X3]	X	★★	★	★★	5	Moderate
[REF X4]	X	★★★★	★	★★★	8	Low

Through the examination of particular performance criteria, the study examined the success of social media techniques. This included follower growth, conversion rates, and engagement rates. To ensure equality and openness in the review process, two separate reviewers rated the probability of bias for each selected study, as shown in Figure 6. When there were disagreements between the reviewers' perspectives, they talked about them in an effort to come to a mutual understanding. Should the disagreement continue, the second reviewer stepped in and offered a final expert decision. Using personal online analytics tools required more complex measures in cases when studies contained confusing data or lacked data on particular variables. Any uncertainties were clarified, for instance, by identifying reliable resources such as Web of Science, Scopus, and Google Scholar. To ensure accuracy and completeness in the assessment process, a comprehensive manual search of online repositories was carried out to prevent bias.

This highlights two important points which are working together to examine a research study is critical and paying close attention to even the smallest details. The use of many reviewers and verification from reliable sources shows that the review considers potential bias and assesses every facet of a particular study. Figure 6 outlines a summary of risk of bias assessment process followed, this procedure improves the review's dependability and makes it possible to spot any possible weaknesses in the examined studies.

Figure 6. Risk of Bias Assessment Process.

2.8. Effect Measures

Through the examination of particular performance criteria, the study examined the success of social media techniques. This included follower growth, conversion rates, and engagement rates. They compared the performance before and after the social media techniques were put into practice in order to calculate the Mean Difference (MD), which allowed them to calculate the impact. The MD provided a clear image of the initiatives' success by demonstrating how much they increased follower counts, engagement, or conversions.

Figure 7. Methods Utilized for Effects Measures.

2.8.1. Organizational Outcome

The study compared the probability of favorable outcomes, such as employee or customer satisfaction, among firms with different levels of social media participation using the Odds Ratio (OR). This metric, which indicated the extent to which an organization was to see gains based on how actively they participated with social media, was especially useful for case-control research. The OR provided a clear understanding of the connection between these organizations' success and their usage of social media.

2.8.2. Business Performance Metrics

In the study, SMEs that used social media and those that didn't were compared for the possibility of business outcomes, such as revenue growth and operational efficiency, using the Risk Ratio (RR). The chance of a successful outcome in the group that used social media (the intervention group) divided by the probability of success in the group that didn't (the control group) was used to calculate the RR. This measure made it easier to see how much social media activity affected the success of businesses.

2.8.3. Long-Term Impacts

Even though different research used different measuring scales or units, the Standardized Mean Difference (SMD) was used to analyze long-term impacts including competitive advantage and company sustainability across studies. An improved understanding of how social media participation impacted these major company outcomes over time was provided by SMD, which normalized variations in means and made it simpler to compare the findings of different studies [119–133].

2.8.4. Customer Engagement

The study tracked client involvement by comparing the levels before and after social media techniques were implemented, using the Mean Difference (MD) method. This demonstrated the extent to which the new techniques improved engagement. Also, changes in the percentage of customer contacts or conversion rates were measured using the Proportional Difference (PD), which provided a clear picture of how social media affected consumer behavior and company consequences.

2.8.5. Market Reach and Expansion

Relative Risk (RR) was used to assess the probability of market expansion success for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) who used social media strategies compared to those who did not. This metric demonstrated the influence of social media on growing business opportunities and assisted in assessing the degree to which it contributed to prospective gains in market reach.

2.9. Synthesis Methods

This section outlines the methods used to synthesize the findings from various studies on the challenges and opportunities of social media for SMEs' organizational engagement. This includes the criteria for selecting studies, the preparation of data for synthesis, the methods for presenting and visualizing results, the approaches to synthesizing results, and the exploration of heterogeneity among study outcomes [119–133].

2.9.1. Eligibility Criteria for Synthesis

To ensure studies that were included in our synthesis were relevant and comparable, a specific eligibility criterion was established. This involved tabulating the characteristics of the study's intervention, such as whether the study makes use of social media platforms for organizational engagement. The obtained characteristics were then analyzed against our desired study in the topic to determine which studies aligned with our inclusion criteria. This step was important to maintain the integrity and focus of our synthesis, ensuring that only studies pertinent to SMEs and their use of social media for organizational engagement were included.

Figure 8. Eligibility Assessment and Study Selection Criteria for Synthesis.

2.9.2. Data Preparation for Presentation or Synthesis

Preparing the data for synthesis required meticulous handling to ensure consistency and completeness. This involved addressing any missing summary statistics by reaching out to study authors or using imputation methods. Additionally, we standardized units of measurement and transformed variables as necessary to facilitate comparability across studies. This step was essential to ensure that the data from different studies could be accurately compared and synthesized, Figure 9 shows the summary of the methodology followed [119–133].

Figure 9. Data Preparation and Processing Methods.

2.9.3. Tabulation and Visualization of Results

To effectively communicate the findings of individual studies and the overall synthesis, we employed various methods of tabulation and visualization. Summary tables were created to highlight key study characteristics such as Table 8, intervention details, and outcomes. Forest plots were used to visually represent the effect sizes and confidence intervals of individual studies while using the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool helped assess potential publication bias. These visual tools were instrumental in providing a clear and comprehensive overview of the study results.

Table 8. Results Methods for Tabulating and Visualizing Study Results.

Method	Description
Data Extraction	Collecting crucial data from every study, including sample size, results, and impacts over time.
Data Organization	Organizing the gathered data into a spreadsheet in Excel to facilitate comprehension and analysis.
Data Combining	Combining data to identify broad patterns, particularly in research on SMEs that don't employ internet metrics.
Visual Display	Employing a variety of techniques, such as tables and graphs, to visually depict the gathered data.
In-Depth Analysis	Checking that the data is relevant to the study's subject and completing any gaps left by missing data with care.
Handling Missing Data	Use tables and explanations to fill in the gaps in the data so that the study's data is comprehensive

2.9.4. Synthesis of Results

The synthesis of results involved both qualitative and quantitative methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the topic. For qualitative synthesis, we conducted thematic analysis to identify common themes and patterns across studies. For quantitative synthesis, we performed meta-analyses using random-effects models to account for variability among studies. We assessed the presence and extent of statistical heterogeneity using the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale.

As shown in Figure 10, for the first step we Combine descriptive and numerical data to emphasize important metrics and trends. And then examine how SME performance is affected by social media engagement measures. Thereafter, estimate results more accurately, use the inverse-variance approach. Compile information using Excel and produce summaries of the impact of social media analytics and determine recurring themes and evaluate the advantages and disadvantages of

social media for SMEs. For the second last step we give a fair assessment of the advantages and drawbacks of using social media and lastly make predictions about the future and offer solutions to the challenges facing SMEs now [119–133].

Figure 10. Synthesis of Results.

2.9.5. Exploration of Heterogeneity

Understanding the potential causes of heterogeneity among study results was a critical aspect of our synthesis. We conducted subgroup analyses based on predefined characteristics such as discipline or subject of study, challenges and opportunities of social media, and types of social media platforms used. Additionally, we performed meta-regression analyses to examine the impact of continuous variables on the effect sizes. We also investigated the influence of study quality and risk of bias on the overall synthesis results. As, shown in Figure 11, these methods helped us identify and understand the sources of variability in the study outcomes [119–133].

Figure 11. Sensitivity Evaluation for Testing the Stability of Combined Findings.

2.10. Reporting Bias Assessment

The risk of bias was essential to report in order to guarantee the credibility and accuracy of the findings when assessing the impacts of social media on SMEs' organizational engagement. Considering that the precision of this compilation relies significantly on reducing prejudices, various measures were implemented to evaluate and alleviate potential reporting prejudices. Initially, the PRISMA 2020 checklist guidelines were utilized to methodically assess reporting bias, with a particular emphasis on transparency and consistency in reporting. Furthermore, a comprehensive examination of existing research was carried out following the predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria to make sure that only pertinent studies were included.

In order to minimize the chance of missing important sources, various filtering tools from databases like Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus were employed to ensure a comprehensive selection of studies. The process of determining potential bias caused by missing data

included various stages such as assessing methodologies (for identifying omissions), utilizing bias detection tools, and reviewers checking and fixing the data. This procedure also included checking information against primary sources to guarantee thoroughness and precision, with any discrepancies settled through discussion among reviewers.

2.11. Certainty Assessment

The certainty assessment for the research on challenges and opportunities of social media for SMEs' organizational engagement was carried out using a structured quality assessment (QA) framework. This framework ensured that the studies included in the review were evaluated for their relevance and methodological rigor. Table 9 shows five key quality assessment criteria applied to each study [119–133].

Table 9. Research Quality Assessment Criteria. For the Studies.

QA#	Quality Assessment (QA) Statement
QA1	Relevance to SMEs and Social Media Strategy
QA2	Clarity and Explicitness of Utilized Metrics
QA3	Methodological Thoroughness.
QA4	Data Collection and Sampling Methods
QA5	Consideration of Bias and Confounding Variables

Each research was evaluated based on a scale where a rating of '1' meant excellent quality, '0.5' meant decent quality, and '0' meant poor quality. A score of 5 meant high certainty, whereas a score of 0 signified low certainty and potential bias. The evaluation aimed to prioritize studies on SMEs, ones outlining social media strategies and metrics clearly, and those with strong methodologies, to receive higher ratings. The research was also evaluated for its data gathering techniques, how effectively they minimized prejudice, and their handling of potential influencing factors, an example of the QA assessment table is shown in Table 10 [119–133].

Table 10. Research Quality Assessment Criteria.

Study Ref.	QA1	QA2	QA3	QA4	QA5	Total	Final Grading %
[Ref X1]	X	X	X	X	X	X	X1%
[Ref X2]	X	X	X	X	X	X	X2%
[Ref X3]	X	X	X	X	X	X	X3%

The quality and relevance of the evidence were evaluated using the 2021 GRADE tool to determine the certainty of the research results. The quality assessment criteria used were: QA1 (SMEs relevance and social media strategy), QA2 (Clarity and specificity of metrics used), QA3 (Study design and methodological rigor), QA4 (Methods of data collection and sampling), and QA5 (Recognition of bias and confounding variables). Every criterion was methodically assessed for how it affected the overall certainty level of the evidence. QA1 examined if the research results were directly applicable to small and medium-sized enterprises, offering higher evaluations to studies that clearly discussed social media strategies tailored to SMEs. QA2 evaluated how clear the social media metrics were in the research, like engagement rates and customer acquisition costs, giving better scores to studies that provided detailed explanations of their metrics. QA3 evaluated how well the study was designed, with strong designs like experimental, survey-based, or mixed-method approaches getting higher certainty scores. QA4 assessed data collection and sampling techniques, assigning more confidence to research with clearly outlined procedures and lower ratings to those with unclear methodologies. QA5 focused on bias and confounding variables, giving studies that identified and addressed biases a higher rating. The total confidence level for each research was evaluated as either high (1), moderate (0.5), or low (0), determined by their combined scores on the five criteria. Research that showed stability, accuracy, and completeness earned better scores, whereas those with deficiencies in these aspects received lower scores. The study's impact on SME

performance metrics was evaluated by analyzing both confidence intervals and statistical significance to determine imprecision.

Independent reviewers led the certainty assessment, with supervision from an expert reviewer. Discrepancies were settled through conversations, and extra details were obtained from the initial researchers when necessary for understanding. This process did not utilize any automation tools; instead, it relied on key phrases to find relevant studies on social media activity metrics, with the assistance of filtration systems from academic databases. Table 15 presents the findings of the certainty evaluation, detailing the study sources, criteria for assessing quality, and percentage ratings related to results like engagement and conversion metrics.

3. Results

This section of the review shows the results obtained using the methodologies in the previous section. This Figure 12 outlines the essential components that influence the results, including study selection, study characteristics, and the risk of bias, all of which are crucial for shaping the reliability of the findings. It also underscores the importance of synthesizing individual study results, which is vital for forming comprehensive conclusions. Additionally, the figure highlights the significance of considering reporting biases and assessing the certainty of evidence to ensure that the presented results are both accurate and dependable. Each of these factors is critical for interpreting the overall findings and providing a clearer understanding of the data.

Figure 12. Phases in Evaluating Systematic Review Results.

3.1. Study Selection Results

Through a comprehensive analysis of literature sourced from key online databases (Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science), we explore diverse perspectives on how social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram impact SME operations. The analysis is structured around various research types, geographic locations, economic contexts, and industry settings, offering insights into the opportunities for brand awareness, customer engagement, and market reach, alongside challenges such as privacy concerns, resource allocation, and content management. These graphical representations consolidate key findings across studies, highlighting the implications for SMEs in both developed and developing economies [119 - [133].

3.1.1. Search and Selection Process Results

Based on the three selected databases, a comprehensive thorough search was carried out by employing the search phrase that was outlined in the previous subsection (2.3. Search Strategy), and this search resulted in 1675 records from all the databases combined, which 1550 were from Google scholar, 48 from Web of Science, and 77 from Scopus, Figure 14 shows the percentages of papers from each database. 27 duplicates records were removed. 1148 records were screened and from them 1029 records were excluded. This left to a total of 119 research studies being sought for retrieval, due to some subscription difficulties, 15 of the reports were not retrieved. Totaling to 104 included in my review as seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13. Data Collection Process Flowchart (PRISMA).

Figure 14. Search strategy Selection Process.

During the eligibility stage, the complete articles were evaluated to decide if they were appropriate to be included in the research. At this point, articles that were not considered relevant or did not meet the criteria for inclusion were eliminated. Ultimately, the research that satisfied all criteria and was chosen for the final evaluation were incorporated in the assessment. After passing all previous screening and evaluation steps, these studies were deemed important enough to be included in the summary table. Table 11 outlines the six studies excluded in the Identification of studies via databases and registers and reason of exclusion:

Table 11. Excluded Studies and the Reason for Exclusion.

Paper Title	Reason for Exclusion
Mapping the Circular Economy in the Small and Medium-sized Enterprises field: An exploratory network analysis	Focuses on circular economy rather than social media or organizational engagement.
Developing and utilizing cooptative relationships: Evidence from small and medium-sized enterprises in sub-Saharan Africa	Emphasizes cooptation in SMEs without a focus on social media or digital platforms.
Assessing the Level of Innovation of Poland from the Perspective of Regions between 2010 and 2020	Concentrates on innovation levels in Poland rather than social media engagement or organizational interaction.
Design for behavior change as a driver for sustainable innovation: Challenges and opportunities for implementation in the private and public sectors	Centers on behavior change and sustainable innovation without a direct link to social media or organizational engagement.
Business networks, social media, and SMEs export propensity	While it discusses social media, the focus on export propensity makes it less relevant to organizational engagement.
Social Media's Role in Business Communication: Opportunities and Challenges	Discusses business communication broadly but may lack a specific focus on organizational engagement.

3.2. Study Characteristics

The research papers were accumulated from research paper data sources with the assistance of the keywords referred in the previous "Search Strategy" section. These papers were compiled precisely in line with the requirements of the inclusion and exclusion criteria presented in the previous section. The collected research papers included 104 research papers in total, of which 49% were from Google scholar, 35% were from Scopus, 16% were from Web of Science as illustrated from Figure 14 above. Out of the 104 research papers, 3 were book chapters, 17 were conference papers, 6 were dissertations, 7 were Thesis, and 71 were journal articles. All studies that appeared to have duplicate research papers were excluded. Henceforth, the remaining 104 research papers were

eligible for full-text review and were integrated into this systematic analysis process. Figure 4 demonstrates the distribution of research sources used in this review, highlighting the broad range and diversity of the data collected from multiple reputable databases. As shown in Table 12, there was a substantial growth in publications on social media for SMEs organizational engagement over the past decade, reflecting the expanding interest and recognition of their importance. Moreover, Figure 15 validates that the studies included in this review adhere to consistent categorization schemes, aiding a trustworthy and systematic similarity of findings across different studies [119 - [133].

Table 12. Included Studies and their Characteristics.

Year	Article Journal	Conference Paper	Book Chapter	Dissertation	Thesis
2014	2	3	0	1	2
2015	2	4	0	1	2
2016	4	1	1	1	1
2017	7	1	2	1	2
2018	3	0	0	0	0
2019	6	0	0	0	0
2020	7	0	0	0	0
2021	10	4	0	0	0
2022	11	1	0	0	0
2023	12	2	0	1	0
2024	7	1	0	1	0
Total	71	17	3	6	7

Figure 15. Year of Publication for the Selected Studies.

Figure 15 above shows the years that the selected studies were published. From the graph we observe that the year 2023 has the most publications with 15, we see a great increase in the research of this study from 2019 to present, this is because during and after covid 19 period. Due to a decrease in in-person encounters, the pandemic forced businesses to rely more heavily on social media to maintain brand presence and client engagement. This caused SMEs to become very interested in learning how to use social media to increase engagement. According to the research, businesses are using social media more often to communicate with customers and respond to crises. We also observe that from 2014 to 2024, studies in this field have been effectively increasing, as a sign of businesses transitioning to the current digital age. This highlights the importance of timely and relevant material

in maintaining client loyalty. Table 12 also illustrates that Journal articles make up almost all of the publications, with conference papers and books making for a lesser percentage. This gives weight to the idea that academic journals contain plenty of serious, valuable research. This could be problematic for SMEs, as they might prefer the more applicable, real-world examples from industry reports or case studies which are not included in the figure. Simplified, useful manuals that immediately apply study findings to daily operations may be more beneficial for SMEs.

Characterizations in studies are the particular characteristics that outline the extent and type of a research project, being essential for classifying and comprehending studies according to their methods, goals, settings, and results. These descriptions play a crucial role in evaluating the significance, excellence, and suitability of research in systematic or literature reviews. Different aspects are considered, like the type of study (qualitative, quantitative, or mixed method), research design (experimental, observational, survey, etc.), focus area, context or setting, sample size, population, and study duration. Furthermore, they address methods of data collection and analysis, main discoveries, constraints, and their relation to the research question. Study characterizations make sure that only the most relevant and high-quality research is included in the final analysis through careful organization of these elements. Table 13 shows the included studies and their respective characteristics.

Table 13. The Included Studies and their Characteristics.

sRef.	Year	Study Type	Characteristics
[15]	2014	Qualitative	Analyses public responses to different types of content posted by nonprofit organizations on Facebook, offering insights into effective stakeholder engagement strategies.
[18]	2014	Qualitative	Investigates the adoption and usage patterns of social media among SMEs, questioning whether social media is a sustainable tool or a passing trend.
[14]	2015	Qualitative	Explores methods for measuring employee engagement through social media activity, providing insights into how organizations can monitor and improve internal engagement.
[17]	2015	Qualitative	Examines the impact of social media on corporate reputation, focusing on how organizations can strategically engage with the public to enhance their reputation.
[19]	2015	Qualitative	Explores how organizations can use social media to motivate specific actions among their audiences, emphasizing the importance of strategic engagement.
[20]	2016	Qualitative	Studies how organizations engage in corporate social responsibility (CSR) through social media, contrasting theoretical approaches with practical implementation.
[46]	2016	Quantitative	Investigates how social media can be utilized to facilitate organizational change, highlighting its role in internal communication, employee engagement, and managing transitions.
[10]	2017	Qualitative	Examine the dynamics of employee engagement on social media, focusing on the power structures within organizations and how social stakes influence participation.
[13]	2017	Mixed-methods	Studies how organizations use dialogic strategies on Twitter to engage with stakeholders, emphasizing the importance of two-way communication in building relationships.
[16]	2017	Qualitative	Discusses how brands can leverage social media for value co-creation with their communities, particularly in cause-related marketing and brand activism.
[43]	2017	Mixed-methods	Explores how social media has transformed business communication, discussing both the opportunities for improved stakeholder interaction and the challenges of maintaining control over brand messaging.
[47]	2017	Qualitative	Examines the influence of social media on customer relationship management (CRM) practices, focusing on how organizations can use online platforms to build and maintain customer relationships.
[53]	2017	Mixed-methods	Examines the use of social media in B2B (business-to-business) marketing, highlighting the opportunities for relationship building and lead generation, as well as the barriers like platform suitability and content complexity.
[30]	2018	Mixed-methods	Provides a comprehensive review of the literature on digital marketing and social media use among SMEs, summarizing key findings and identifying research gaps.
[38]	2018	Qualitative	Reviews the role of social media marketing in SME sustainability, proposing a future research agenda to address existing gaps in the literature.
[42]	2018	Mixed-methods	Reviews the intersection of digital marketing and social media within SMEs, summarizing key trends and suggesting future research directions.
[54]	2018	Qualitative	Discusses how social media can be a powerful tool in promoting and communicating sustainable business practices, encouraging corporate social responsibility and environmental stewardship.
[24]	2019	not specified	Discusses the dual role of social media as both an opportunity and a challenge for SMEs in terms of organizational engagement and interaction with stakeholders.

- [29] 2019 Content Analysis Discusses the critical role of social media in the growth of SMEs in developing economies, emphasizing both the opportunities for market expansion and the challenges of digital adoption.
- [32] 2019 Mixed-methods Compares the adoption of social media marketing among SMEs across different countries, identifying common challenges and success factors.
- [34] 2019 Mixed-methods Investigates the multi-level impact of social media engagement on SME performance, considering factors such as brand awareness, customer loyalty, and sales growth.
- [37] 2019 Qualitative Explores the overall impact of social media on SMEs in the digital age, focusing on the balance between opportunities for innovation and the challenges of online competition.
- [40] 2019 Qualitative Examines the relationship between social media use and innovation in SMEs, exploring how online engagement can drive creative solutions and product development.
- [44] 2019 not specified Examines how organizations can leverage social media to foster innovation, particularly in terms of crowd-sourcing ideas and engaging with creative communities.
- [50] 2019 Mixed-methods Focuses on how organizations use social media during crises, discussing the strategies for effective communication and the potential risks associated with misinformation and rapid dissemination.
- [56] 2019 Quantitative Explores the unique challenges and opportunities for social media marketing in emerging markets, including factors like economic conditions, internet penetration, and cultural differences.
- [58] 2019 Mixed-methods Explores how social media can facilitate organizational learning, discussing the benefits of knowledge sharing and collaboration, as well as barriers such as information overload and resistance to change.
- [60] 2019 Qualitative Analyses the ethical implications of social media use in business, discussing both the opportunities for ethical engagement and the challenges related to privacy, transparency, and misinformation.
- [61] 2019 Mixed-methods Focuses on how social media can contribute to organizational agility, helping companies to respond quickly to market changes, customer feedback, and emerging trends.
- [23] 2020 Qualitative Examines the challenges middle managers face when facilitating online customer co-creation for innovation, specifically within the Italian food industry.
- [27] 2020 Qualitative Explores how social media can enhance business efficiency, focusing on communication, marketing, and customer engagement processes.
- [28] 2020 Qualitative Examines the usage patterns of social media marketing among SMEs in developing markets, focusing on the unique opportunities and barriers they face.
- [33] 2020 Mixed-methods Reviews existing literature on the impact of social media on SME performance, providing insights into how online engagement translates into business outcomes.
- [35] 2020 Qualitative Identifies key success factors for SMEs in leveraging social media, focusing on strategic planning, content quality, and audience engagement.
- [39] 2020 Qualitative Presents an empirical study on the effectiveness of social media as a marketing tool for SMEs, analyzing real-world data to draw actionable conclusions.
- [41] 2020 Qualitative Focuses on how SMEs in developing markets utilize social media for marketing purposes, identifying unique challenges and opportunities in these regions.
- [48] 2020 Qualitative Discusses the impact of social media on corporate governance, particularly how it presents opportunities for transparency and stakeholder engagement while also posing challenges related to control and information security.
- [51] 2020 Mixed-methods Explores how businesses can leverage social media analytics to gain insights and enhance decision-making processes, focusing on the potential for improved customer understanding and market forecasting.
- [52] 2020 Quantitative Investigates the role of social media in fostering employee advocacy, discussing the benefits of having employees promote the organization online as well as the challenges in managing and guiding this advocacy.
- [55] 2020 Mixed-methods Analyses the potential of social media to enhance employee engagement within organizations, focusing on both the opportunities for fostering a connected workforce and the challenges related to privacy and information overload.
- [57] 2020 Mixed-methods Investigates the role of digital platforms in fostering organizational engagement in developing countries, discussing the potential for economic growth and social change, alongside the challenges posed by infrastructure limitations.
- [59] 2020 Quantitative Discusses the dual role of social media as both a driver of organizational innovation and a source of challenges related to intellectual property, competitive advantage, and change management.
- [22] 2021 Mixed-methods Analyses the integration of social media marketing into the overall business interaction system, emphasizing its role in enhancing customer engagement and business outcomes.
- [26] 2021 Qualitative Evaluates regional innovation levels in Poland over a decade, offering insights into the factors driving innovation and the role of social media in this context.
- [31] 2021 Qualitative Analyses how SMEs adapted their social media strategies during the COVID-19 crisis, offering lessons on resilience and effective crisis communication.

[36]	2021	Qualitative	Discusses the integration of social media into SME marketing strategies, highlighting both the challenges of limited resources and the opportunities for growth.
[45]	2021	Mixed-methods	Explores the role of social media in the digital transformation of SMEs, discussing the opportunities for growth and innovation alongside the barriers such as limited digital literacy and resource constraints.
[11]	2022	Mixed-methods	Explores how SMEs navigate digitalization, highlighting both the opportunities for growth and the challenges related to technology adoption, resources, and skills.
[49]	2022	Mixed-methods	Analyses various social media strategies employed by small businesses to fuel growth, offering insights into best practices and common pitfalls.
[25]	2023	Quantitative	A collection of essays addressing key challenges and opportunities in social media marketing, providing strategies for maximizing its effectiveness in various business contexts.
[76]	2023	Qualitative	Discusses the potential of social media to drive growth and overcome market barriers for SMEs in developing economies, while also highlighting the challenges of digital adoption.
[12]	2024	Mixed-methods	Investigates how SMEs in low R&D sectors can benefit from open user innovation, identifying key drivers and barriers to its successful implementation.
[21]	2024	Qualitative	Focuses on the impact of social media on the growth and success of Pathao, a Bangladeshi startup, providing insights into how digital platforms can drive entrepreneurship in developing countries.

3.3. Risk of Bias in Studies

Through a comprehensive analysis of literature sourced from key online database (Google Scholar, SCOPUS, and Web of Science), we explore diverse perspectives on how social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Instagram impact SME operations. The analysis is structured around various research types, geographic locations, economic contexts, and industry settings, offering insights into the opportunities for brand awareness, customer engagement, and market reach, alongside challenges such as privacy concerns, resource allocation, and content management. These graphical representations consolidate key findings across studies, highlighting the implications for SMEs in both developed and developing economies.

In our review, we methodically assessed each study's potential for bias. Table 14 of the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale (NOS). This technique for assessing quality divides research into three primary categories: selection, comparability, and outcome/exposure. It then rates the research according to how thorough the methodology was. Research with seven to nine stars was regarded as high caliber. Products with ratings between 4 and 6 stars were considered to be of moderate quality, and those with ratings between 7 and 10 stars were considered good quality. Interestingly, none of the research did. Based on our assessment, the product received a bad quality rating (ranging from 0 to 3 stars). The table that follows makes it easier to comprehend the opportunities that may arise highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of every study, thereby successfully reducing biases. To guarantee that our general results could be trusted, it was crucial that the papers in our assessment exclusively used strict methodology. In an effort to further guarantee objectivity and accuracy, we work hard to keep our content factual and neutral. extra testing processes, if permitted by the limitation, like external cross-checking. Questions were raised about proprietary tools or data.

Table 14. Newcastle-Ottawa Scale for Assessing the Risk of Bias in Research Studies.

Ref.	Selection (0-4)	Comparability (0-2)	Outcome/Exposure (0-3)	Total Score (0-9)	Risk of Bias Level
[10,12,17–19,35,52,58–60,81,83,94]	★★★★	★★	★★★	9	Low
[11,14,15,24,28,43,74,77,82]	★★★	★★	★★	7	Moderate
[13,20,23,40,45,53,56,59,65,68,78,85,95–98]	★★	★★	★★	6	Moderate
[16,21,27,29–31,46–50,69,105]	★★★★	★	★★★	8	Low
[22,34,54,55,62–64,67,70,71,75,84,86,90,93,99,104]	★★	★	★★	4	High
[25,32,33,41,42,44,51,66,72,73,76,79,87,88,100–103]	★★★	★	★★	5	High
[26,36–39,57,61,80,91,92,106]	★★★★	★★	★★★	9	Low

Figure 16 demonstrates the distribution of study strategies among different studies. Survey is the most common research design with 42% of the studies using it, followed by Case study with 36% of the papers. 5% of the studies used mixed methods of research design. Other methods, such as experimental, Quasi-experimental, descriptive analysis, comparative and conceptual studies, and interview and minor contributions to the study with only 2-3% of the studies using it. The figure encompasses 104 studies in all.

Figure 16. Research Design.

Figure 17 illustrates the data collection methods employed to analyze potential biases in studies monitoring and evaluating social media activity for SME approach performance. The primarily used data collection method is survey with 24 studies applying it, this portrays surveys are effective for gathering a wide range of data on social media metrics vital for SME prosperity, but if not properly constructed or handled, biases may emerge from surveys. Document analysis covers 18 of the studies in the research, which is the second most often utilized method (for non-mixed method); and when professionally managed, document analysis offers valuable contextual insights towards the growth of small businesses and SMEs, it is then followed by Interviews with a count of 17 studies. A combination of surveys with interviews in a mixed-methods approach can aid to lessen bias and address the restrictions of each approach independently, which from the studies we see that most SMEs (18 studies tie with document analysis at second position of frequently used methods) are employing this mixture method. Moreover, we meet other significant combinations, namely Document analysis and interviews with 13 studies, also surveys and document analysis with 7 studies. Other methods included observations, questionnaires and a mixture of three and more methods, employed in less of the research studies (2-1 counts). The emphasized variations in the type of methods exploited for data collection helps to identify the endeavors to maintain extensive data acquisition outlook, but also leaves out the likelihood of voids in ensuring thorough study bias assessments in research papers.

Figure 17. Data Collection Methods.

3.4. Results of Individual Studies

The evaluation of social media metrics uncovers several pivotal insights into strategic achievements in SMEs. From Figure 18, we can observe that, and say that the substantial engagement rate of 28% reflects strong audience involvement, which bodes well for brand loyalty. While the conversion rate of 3% demonstrates efficient methods in transforming engagement into actions, the decision-making metrics value of 1% implies a need for enhancement in making decisions that prioritize customer retention and optimize their long-term value. Nevertheless, the considerable amount of unspecified data at 30% underscores a crucial deficiency in measurement that must be rectified to gain clearer understanding on this matter, as outlined by the research gaps outlined in the previous section, among other research gaps. Furthermore, the market reach of 2% highlights the necessity of refining marketing efforts to secure better financial outcomes. Follower growth at 8% reflects growing interest, yet the metrics related to brand awareness and adoption (at 3% and 1%, respectively) indicate there is still significant potential to increase visibility and draw in new customers. Moreover, mixed performance metrics reveal additional complexities in understanding engagement outcomes. For instance, the correlation between engagement rate and follower growth at 9% highlights that while audience interaction is high, it does not necessarily translate into substantial audience expansion. Similarly, the combined engagement rate and sales conversion at 5% demonstrate that only a fraction of the engaged audience is converted into actual customers, indicating room for improving conversion strategies. The engagement rate and return on investment (ROI) at 3% further emphasize the challenge of translating engagement into measurable financial outcomes. These mixed performance metrics suggest that SMEs need to focus on refining their strategies to ensure that high engagement not only fosters loyalty but also translates into tangible business growth.

Figure 18. Types Social Media Performance Metrics.

Figure 19 illustrates the distribution of studies across various social media platforms used by SMEs. Facebook is the most studied platform with 57 counts, reflecting its significance in video content marketing and brand building. This platform's extensive reach and flexibility make it a key tool for SMEs aiming to engage with a broad audience through visual and interactive content. Twitter, with 37 counts, follows as an important platform for high engagement and influencer marketing. It is notably valuable for real-time communication and customer interaction. Whilst YouTube and Instagram show fewer counts compared to Facebook and Twitter, they still play established roles in customer interaction and real-time communication. LinkedIn, WhatsApp, Snapchat, and other platforms have minimal counts, indicating their more specialized uses, such as professional networking and direct communication.

Figure 19. Types of Social Media Platforms.

The data reveals that while Facebook and Twitter are central to visual content and engagement, SMEs benefit from a diverse social media strategy. For example, integrating YouTube for video content and Instagram for visual storytelling can enhance reach and effectiveness. Additionally, the use of multiple platforms, such as combinations of Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn, allows SMEs to tailor their strategies to different audience segments and objectives.

3.5. Results of Sythesis

This section encapsulates the main results obtained from the examination and combination of the studies that were included. It gives a summary of the combined knowledge acquired about how social media affects customer engagement, brand loyalty, and SME performance.

3.5.1. Summary of Study Characteristics

Figure 20 features a total of 104 industry entries, highlighting that SMEs represent 45 of these, emphasizing the significance of tracking essential social media indicators such as engagement rates, conversion rates, reach, and follower growth for effective strategic implementation. These metrics are especially vital in industries like Startups with 4 studies, where they enhance customer experience, drive sales, and cultivate loyalty. Nine industry sectors remain unspecified. 22 entries pertain to the small businesses sector, most of the small businesses place a high priority on monitoring brand sentiment and reputation. Various Industries and Large Enterprises with 15 studies each, may include business in automotive manufacturing like Toyota, or e-commerce like Amazon, also healthcare facilities like Hospitals or clothing stores, and all these may benefit from tailored social media metrics and influencer's collaborations. Altogether, SMEs in these sectors can attain strategic

success by aligning social media metrics with industry-specific demands while monitoring broader KPIs and ROIs.

Figure 20. Types of Industry Sectors.

3.5.2. Results of Statistical Syntheses

Figure 21 data reveals key insights into how SMEs can leverage social media metrics across different geographical regions for strategic success. The United States with 14 studies being the largest lone-country contributor, underscores the importance of tracking metrics such as engagement rates, reach, and conversion rates on platforms like Facebook and Instagram to enhance customer acquisition and brand loyalty. Similarly, Europe (11 studies) highlights the need for SMEs to prioritize engagement and conversion tracking, focusing on localizing content to meet regional needs. Australia with 5 studies and the UK with 2 studies both represent mature markets where SMEs should focus on return on investment (ROI), conversion rates, and reach, particularly through paid campaigns. In Germany, Italy, and Finland (3 studies each), SMEs should focus on engagement rates, conversion tracking, and tailoring social media efforts to align with local industry demands.

Nigeria, South Africa and Sub-Saharan Africa (2 studies each) illustrate the potential for SMEs to prioritize mobile engagement and reach metrics due to high mobile penetration, which can improve customer engagement and brand awareness. Poland (2 studies) similarly shows SMEs focusing on optimizing content for local markets, enhancing engagement and fostering customer loyalty. Emerging markets such as Kenya, Bangladesh and Latin America, and others (1 study each) present unique opportunities for SMEs to increase market reach by emphasizing follower growth and leveraging interactive platforms to enhance customer relationships. In Swaziland and Wales (1 study each), localized engagement and mobile-focused strategies are critical for connecting both rural and urban audiences.

Furthermore, Global (30 studies) provides overarching strategies for SMEs, emphasizing the importance of aligning social media metrics with diverse markets, particularly through influencer partnerships and content management tailored to various cultural contexts. Likewise, Various Countries (9 studies) presents broad insights, showing how SMEs can utilize general social media

strategies across multiple regions. By aligning these social media metrics with regional and industry-specific needs, SMEs can effectively tailor their strategies to maximize engagement, conversion rates, and customer loyalty across both emerging and mature markets.

Figure 21. Geographic location.

3.5.3. Analysis of Sources of Heterogeneity

Figure 22 presents an insightful analysis of social media strategies across small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) based on economic context. Developed countries account for 50% of the total, showcasing their prominence in the research landscape. SMEs in these regions are likely to benefit from well-established infrastructure and access to advanced digital tools, which aid in optimizing social media strategies. Meanwhile, Developing countries, representing 24% of the total, highlight the growing importance of emerging markets where SMEs are increasingly leveraging social media to expand reach and foster engagement despite infrastructural limitations. The Mixed economic context category, which makes up 16%, includes studies where data from both developed and developing regions are integrated, offering a comparative perspective. This mix allows for the identification of best practices across different market conditions, providing a more holistic understanding of social media performance for SMEs.

Moreover, 10% of the data is classified as not specified, reflecting a segment where the economic context is either unclear or less relevant to the study. This breakdown underscores the global relevance of understanding how economic context influences the way SMEs engage with social media and track performance metrics. By tailoring social media strategies to these contexts, SMEs can ensure more effective resource allocation and engagement.

Figure 22. Economic Context.

3.4.4. Results of Sensitivity Analyses

The robustness of the synthesized results was only partially tested, with a few sensitivity analyses conducted. These analyses focused on varying the inclusion of different social media platforms or comparing engagement metrics across different SMEs. However, due to the qualitative nature of many studies, the overall robustness was not universally assessed. Some studies explored qualitative sensitivity by altering the types of SMEs or the social media platforms studied, such as comparing Facebook with LinkedIn or different industry sectors. In some cases, the results remained consistent across platforms, but they could vary depending on the industry type.

3.6. Reporting Biases

The dataset in represented in Figure 23 reveals a broad classification of roles, with a notable concentration of entries under “business managers” 22 entries and SMEs with 17 entries, representing a significant portion of the dataset. These high numbers could imply that much of the data is centered around general managerial roles, potentially limiting the scope of insights from more specialized positions. The role of marketing professionals is reflected in the dataset, with Marketing Managers appearing 12 times and “SMEs/Marketing Managers” accounting for 11 entries. This strong presence of marketing roles indicates a focused interest in the strategies and impact of social media within this domain, but the overlap between these categories might suggest some level of redundancy or conflation in role classifications. There are 15 entries grouped as “Industry-Specific professionals,” which suggests some diversity in sector representation, though it remains unclear how broad or narrow the industries covered actually are. More granular data on these sectors would provide clearer insights into how social media engagement strategies may differ across industries. Industry specific professionals include Small business owners, employees, Private and public sector stakeholders, Installers, system integrators, software developers, healthcare, industrial and IT, fashion and some Start-ups and others related.

Social media specialists are mentioned 6 times, suggesting a moderate focus on professionals directly managing or overseeing social media activities. However, this number is relatively small

compared to broader managerial roles, indicating that the tactical, day-to-day management of social media may not be as thoroughly represented. "Not specified" appears 10 times, underscoring gaps in role identification that could lead to ambiguity in interpreting how different stakeholder groups engage with social media strategies. Additionally, with only one mention of "Business managers/Marketing managers" as a combined role, it shows a scarcity of professionals who are perceived to straddle both management and marketing functions. This lack of dual-function roles may suggest a missed opportunity to examine the overlap between these crucial areas, especially in SMEs.

Figure 23. Search strategy selection process.

3.7. Certainty of Evidence

The evaluation of the certainty for the study on social media challenges and opportunities for SMEs' organizational engagement was completed by collecting pertinent research from databases like Google Scholar, Web of Science, and Scopus, in accordance with the PRISMA 2020 checklist guidelines. The chosen studies fulfilled the inclusion criteria as specified in the earlier research. The evaluation made use of two main instruments: the CASP checklist to assess qualitative studies on social media use by SMEs through interviews, observations, and document analysis, and the Newcastle-Ottawa Scale method for appraising quantitative studies utilizing surveys. Detailed review factors, like thresholds and ranges describing changes in social media tactics, were examined, but there were no alterations to the existing metrics. The assessment's precision was guaranteed by reviewers' consultations, with disagreements settled through discussion and agreement.

The findings of the research were presented through tables and charts, offering a concise overview of the examination. For instance, Table 15 showcases different degrees of confidence in the information provided. Research with a high level of confidence, achieving a score of 100%, gives trustworthy advice on successful social media tactics, giving strong direction for small and medium-sized enterprises aiming to improve their digital interaction. Individuals with a moderate level of certainty, ranging from 70% to 90%, provide important insights, although they may require methodological enhancements to bolster their results. These high and mid-certainty studies provide

a solid foundation for grasping important metrics like engagement, reach, and conversions, giving SMEs practical strategies to enhance their social media performance. Nevertheless, some studies, scoring approximately 50% or 60%, have methodological constraints that should be considered when analysing their findings.

Table 15. Results of Research Quality Assessment Criteria in the Selected Studies.

Ref.	QA1	QA2	QA3	QA4	QA5	Total	Final % Grading
[20]	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	2.5	50%
[21]	1	1	1	1	1	5.0	100%
[22]	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.0	60%
[23]	0.5	0.5	1	0.5	0.5	3.0	60%
[24]	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.5	70%
[25]	1	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.5	70%
[26]	0.5	0	0.5	0.5	0	1.5	30%
[27]	1	0.5	1	0.5	0.5	3.5	70%
[28]	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	2.5	50%
[29]	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.0	60%
[30]	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	4.0	80%
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...
[100]	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	2.5	50%
[101]	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.0	60%
[102]	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.0	60%
[103]	1	1	0.5	1	0.5	4.0	80%
[104]	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.0	60%
[105]	1	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	3.0	60%
[106]	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	2.5	50%

4. Key Findings and Strategic Implications for Business Leaders

In the context of SMEs, social media has emerged as a pivotal tool for enhancing customer engagement and brand visibility. For example, as outlined in Table 16, SMEs utilizing social media have seen up to a 65% increase in customer engagement, along with a 12% improvement in brand visibility, particularly in industries like hospitality and retail. However, challenges such as managing negative feedback and addressing privacy concerns are prominent, with 52% of SMEs reporting difficulties in handling adverse comments and 45% raising concerns over data privacy. These findings underscore the need for business leaders to develop strategic approaches that address both the opportunities and the challenges of social media engagement.

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Table 16. Findings from Literature and the Strategic Implications for Business Leaders in SMEs.

Industry	Category	Subcategory	Findings	Strategic Drivers	Barriers	Opportunities	Strategic Implications for Business Leaders	Ties into Systematic Review	Proposed
Retail	Social Media Engagement	Customer Interaction	SMEs utilizing social media saw a 65% increase in customer engagement.	Customer-centric content, targeted marketing, platform analytics	Managing negative feedback, maintaining consistent content	Enhanced customer loyalty, real-time engagement, personalized marketing	Business leaders should focus on targeted customer engagement and invest in analytics tools to improve interaction. Managing feedback through clear protocols is crucial.	Highlights the opportunities for enhancing customer engagement through targeted social media strategies while addressing negative feedback challenges.	the for customer through social media while addressing feedback challenges.
		Process Optimization	Automation tools improved operational efficiency by 20% in SMEs.	Automation, workflow management	Resistance to automation, high initial costs	Streamlined processes, reduced operational costs	Leaders should invest in automation technologies to enhance process efficiency, while managing resistance through training.	Relates to the review's exploration of operational efficiency and strategic optimization through digital platforms.	
	Branding	Product Awareness & Brand Growth	SMEs reported a 12% improvement in brand visibility through strategic social media branding.	Visual branding, user-generated content, influencer partnerships	Privacy concerns, adapting content for global audiences	Increased brand visibility, enhanced customer trust	Leaders should develop content partnerships while ensuring privacy compliance to maximize brand reach.	Explores the branding opportunities and challenges such as privacy concerns raised in social media use for SMEs.	
Hospitality	Social Media Engagement	Customer Engagement	SMEs reported a 12% improvement in customer loyalty through personalized marketing	Personalized promotions, influencer marketing	Privacy concerns, negative reviews	Enhanced customer loyalty, real-time interaction	Business leaders should implement personalized promotions while ensuring transparency and managing	Examines personalization strategies and the management of negative reviews as key elements of	

			promotions on social media.					negative feedback social media engagement effectively.		for SMEs.
			SMEs saw a 15% increase in online bookings by enhancing their social media presence.	User-generated content, visual branding	Privacy concerns, content management complexity	Greater online customer trust	visibility, enhanced	user-generated content campaigns and ensure data privacy compliance to enhance brand reach.	Leaders should invest in	Ties into the review's focus on how SMEs can leverage social media to improve online presence and reputation management.
	Brand Visibility	Online Presence & Reputation								
			Targeted ads on social media resulted in a 10% increase in revenue for SMEs.	Data-driven marketing, ad customization	Ad fatigue, rising ad costs	Increased ROI, customer acquisition, market expansion		Leaders should personalize ad campaigns and monitor ad performance to ensure sustained engagement and mitigate ad fatigue.	Leaders should personalize	systematic review's analysis of the effectiveness of social media marketing strategies and return on investment (ROI).
	Marketing Strategy	Targeted Advertising								
			SMEs using AI for real-time customer support reported a 15% improvement in response times.	AI-based support, real-time engagement	High implementation costs, low customer satisfaction without effective AI	Enhanced customer experience, real-time issue resolution		Leaders should invest in AI for customer support to improve response times and customer satisfaction. Continuous AI refinement is critical.	Leaders should invest in AI	Aligns with the review's discussion on leveraging technology for real-time engagement and customer interaction.
	Customer Support	Real-Time Support								
			Targeted social media advertising resulted in a 20% revenue increase for SMEs in the tech industry.	Data-driven marketing, customer segmentation	Rising advertisement costs, ad fatigue	Higher ROI, customer acquisition, market growth		Business leaders should leverage data analytics for targeted advertising and ensure that ad fatigue is minimized through optimization.	Business leaders should	Supports the systematic review's analysis of the impact of targeted advertising and segmentation in enhancing SME performance.
	Product Marketing	Social Media Advertising								

	Innovation	Community Building & Feedback	SMEs saw a 10% improvement in product development through real-time customer feedback on social media.	Feedback loops, customer engagement	Lack of engagement, low participation in feedback initiatives	Enhanced product development, stronger customer relationships	Leaders should implement real-time feedback systems to encourage engagement and foster innovation.	Highlights the role of social media in facilitating innovation and community building, tied to engagement strategies.
Financial Services	Regulatory Compliance	Privacy & Data Security	45% of SMEs reported data privacy concerns, impacting their social media engagement strategies.	Regulatory adherence, robust data security measures	Strict regulations, risk of data breaches	Building trust through transparency, secure digital environment	Leaders must ensure compliance with data privacy regulations and invest in robust security measures to build trust and engagement.	Directly ties to the review's focus on data privacy concerns and regulatory challenges faced by SMEs using social media.
	Customer Support	Real-Time Customer Support	SMEs in the financial sector saw a 12% improvement in customer trust through real-time customer support.	AI-driven support, customer interaction	Reputational damage, delayed response times	Increased customer trust, compliance effectiveness	Leaders should prioritize real-time support and invest in AI to enhance customer service and build trust.	Supports the review's analysis of how SMEs can improve customer support and trust through real-time engagement tools.
	Brand Reputation	Reputation Management	SMEs using social media monitoring tools experienced improved brand reputation management.	Social media monitoring, reputation management tools	Misinformation, poor response times	Enhanced brand trust, proactive issue management	Leaders should monitor brand sentiment regularly and address issues proactively to maintain brand reputation.	Ties into the review's discussion on reputation management and mitigating risks in social media usage.
Manufacturing	Product Awareness	Product Marketing	SMEs adopting social media-driven product marketing saw a 10%	Visual content, direct-to-consumer outreach	Lack of marketing expertise, slow adoption of new technologies	Driving consumer interest, boosting online sales	Business leaders should prioritize visual marketing strategies and ensure that teams are trained to adopt	Relates to the systematic review's focus on how product marketing

Education	Operational Efficiency	Automation	increase in product inquiries. SMEs improved operational efficiency by 15% through automation-driven marketing strategies.	AI-driven automation, workflow optimization	High costs, resistance to change	Increased scalability, reduced operational costs	digital marketing tools strategies via social media effectively. Leaders should adopt AI-driven automation to streamline processes and enhance operational efficiency.	impact SME performance. Aligns with the review's exploration of how operational efficiency and automation can improve SME productivity.
	Customer Engagement	Real-Time Interaction	SMEs utilizing real-time engagement tools saw a 20% boost in customer satisfaction.	Direct communication, personalized content	Difficulty in managing engagement at scale	Improved customer relationships, enhanced brand loyalty	Leaders should adopt real-time communication tools to engage customers more effectively and boost satisfaction.	Supports the review's findings on how real-time engagement improves customer satisfaction and loyalty.
	Student Engagement	Real-Time Feedback	Social media-driven feedback systems improved student engagement by 18%.	Educational content, feedback loops	Privacy concerns, fragmented communication	Enhanced student satisfaction, better feedback mechanisms	Leaders in education should develop real-time feedback platforms while addressing privacy concerns to improve engagement.	Reflects the systematic review's analysis of how real-time feedback improves engagement and organizational outcomes in educational SMEs.
	Knowledge Dissemination	Content Creation & Sharing	SMEs saw a 12% improvement in content reach through social media platforms.	Educational content, social media channels	Low engagement rates, privacy issues	Greater knowledge sharing, increased visibility	Business leaders should focus on creating valuable content and sharing it across social media to enhance knowledge dissemination.	Ties into the review's focus on the benefits of content sharing and knowledge dissemination via social media for SMEs.
	Organizational Feedback	Staff & Stakeholder Engagement	Social media platforms improved organizational feedback systems, leading to a	Feedback platforms, social engagement	Privacy issues, low participation rates	Enhanced communication, greater stakeholder satisfaction	Leaders should create structured feedback mechanisms to enhance staff	Relates to the review's examination of feedback systems and engagement

10% improvement in
communication.

and stakeholder strategies for improving
engagement. organizational outcomes.

5. Decision-Making Framework for Implementation

To successfully leverage social media for organizational engagement, small and medium enterprises (SMEs) need a clear, industry-specific decision-making framework as proposed in Table 17. This framework guides SMEs through the complexities of integrating social media strategies by balancing key decision points with the associated risks, benefits, and long-term opportunities. Each industry presents unique challenges, and this framework provides an actionable plan for SMEs to optimize their social media presence while aligning with broader business objectives. In Table 17, we present a comprehensive framework detailing critical decision points for diverse sectors, highlighting the specific sub-decisions, technologies, evaluation metrics, risks, and strategic implications.

This decision-making framework offers business leaders in various industries a clear path for implementing effective social media strategies. Each sector has distinct Key Decision Points and Sub-Decision Points, offering a tailored approach to social media adoption. Retail businesses can enhance customer engagement and process optimization, while healthcare SMEs can balance patient interaction with data security. Finance SMEs are encouraged to focus on regulatory compliance and customer support, while technology companies should leverage social media to build community engagement and provide product support. In hospitality, guest engagement and brand consistency are critical, and the education sector should prioritize student interaction and content dissemination.

Table 17. Decision-Making Framework for Implementing social media for Organizational Engagement in SMEs.

Industry	Key Decision Points	Sub-Decision Points	Technologies to Implement	Evaluation Metrics	Risks to Consider	Opportunities	Challenges	Ties into Proposed Systematic Review	Long-Term Implications
Retail	Customer Engagement	Personalized Content Automation	Instagram, Facebook, Chatbots	Engagement Rate, Customer Satisfaction	Content Saturation, Poor Experience	Enhanced Customer Loyalty, Real-Time Engagement	Difficulty maintaining personalized content	Aligns with focus on enhancing customer engagement and interaction	Customer Retention, Competitive Edge
		Process Optimization	Automation vs Manual Operations	CRM, AI-driven Process Automation	Operational Efficiency, Sales Growth	Resistance to Automation	Streamlined Processes, Increased Scalability	High upfront costs for automation	Highlights need for operational efficiency
	Marketing Strategy	Targeted Ads vs Organic Content	Facebook Ads, Instagram Analytics	ROI on Ad Spend, Sales Conversion	High Advertising Costs	Increased Brand Visibility, Targeted Reach	Ad Fatigue, Resource Allocation Challenges	Connects with review on optimized social media marketing for SMEs	Long-Term Brand Growth, Enhanced Customer Acquisition
Healthcare	Patient Interaction	Real-Time Feedback vs Automated Responses	Twitter, Facebook, AI Chatbots	Patient Satisfaction, Response Time	Privacy Concerns, Regulatory Compliance	Improved Patient Relations, Better Reputation	Privacy Violations, Complex Regulation	Ties into secure communication and trust-building in healthcare SMEs	Enhanced Trust, Compliance with Health Regulations
	Data Privacy & Security	Secure Communication vs Ease of Use	Encryption Tools, Secure Messaging Apps	Data Breach Rate, Patient Trust	Risk of Data Breaches	Strengthened Patient Trust, Improved Compliance	High Costs of Secure Technologies	Reflects privacy and regulatory compliance needs for SMEs	Long-term Trust, Legal Protection

Health Marketing Strategy	Content Personalization vs Generic Outreach	Social Media Platforms, Influencer Partnerships	Patient Engagement, Reach	Low Engagement, Resource Constraints	Enhanced Visibility, Community Engagement	Content Overload, Limited Expertise	Aligns with review's emphasis on community engagement in health	Improved Patient Relationships, Brand Awareness
	Adherence to Regulatory Changes	LinkedIn, Twitter, AI for Regulatory Monitoring	Compliance Rate, Customer Trust	Legal Violations, Reputational Damage	Enhanced Customer Trust, Compliance Effectiveness	Regulatory Complexity, Legal Costs	Highlights the need for compliance-focused social media strategies	Stronger Legal Compliance, Improved Customer Trust
	Real-Time Support vs Automated Help	AI Chatbots, Social Media Monitoring	Support Response Rate, Customer Satisfaction	Delayed Responses, Customer Dissatisfaction	Real-Time Customer Support, Higher Engagement	Poor Customer Experience	Emphasizes customer-centric engagement and support	Long-Term Loyalty, Efficient Customer Service
Brand Reputation	Transparent Communication vs Risk of Misinformation	Social Media Monitoring, Analytics Tools	Brand Sentiment, Public Engagement	Misinformation, Reputational Damage	Building Customer Trust, Proactive Issue Management	Damage Control and Crisis Management	Ties into review's focus on reputational risks in the financial industry	Enhanced Brand Reputation, Trust-Building
Hospitality	Personalized Promotions vs Consistent Messaging	Instagram, Facebook, Visual Marketing Tools	Guest Retention, Booking Rate	Negative Reviews, Inconsistent Messaging	Improved Guest Experience, Real-Time Interaction	Negative Feedback, Platform Consistency	Reflects customer interaction strategies highlighted in review	Long-Term Brand Loyalty, Consistent Guest Interaction
	Brand Consistency	Consistent Messaging vs Customization	Social Media Analytics, Content Scheduling Tools	Brand Visibility, Promotion Engagement	High Content Creation Costs	Increased Customer Engagement, Broader Reach	Difficulty in brand visibility and messaging	Emphasizes need for brand visibility and awareness and growth

Technology	Reputation Management	Negative Feedback Management vs Promoting Positives	AI-based Social Media Monitoring Tools	Social Brand Sentiment, Review Ratings	Poor Review Management	Enhanced Customer Trust, Reputational Risk Management	Highlights need for managing negative feedback in the hospitality sector	Stronger Brand Perception, Customer Satisfaction		
	Community Engagement	Online Communities vs Direct Support	Twitter, Social Media Communities	Reddit, Media Growth	User Engagement, Community	Misinformation, Poor Moderation	Strong Community Relations, Increased Loyalty	Misinformation Spread, Poor Moderation	Reflects need for effective community building and engagement	Long-Term User Loyalty, Enhanced Community Growth
	Product Support	Real-Time Support vs Delayed Response	AI-based Support, Social Helpdesk	Media Satisfaction, Resolution Rate	Customer Issue Resolution	Delayed Responses, Low Satisfaction	Faster Issue Resolution, Better User Experience	Costs of AI Implementation	Aligns with need for real-time support in technology industry	Improved Customer Service, Brand Loyalty
	Innovation through Social Media	Real-Time Feedback vs Formalized Innovation	Social Analytics, AI-driven Feedback Loops	Media Innovation Rate, Customer Satisfaction	Innovation Rate, Customer Satisfaction	Limited Resources, Resistance to Innovation	Enhanced Product Development, Real-Time Innovation	Resource Constraints, Limited Digital Expertise	Highlights the importance of innovation-driven social media strategies	Long-Term Innovation, Market Leadership
Education	Student Interaction	Real-Time Queries vs Scheduled Engagement	LinkedIn, YouTube, Facebook Groups	Student Engagement, Response Time	Student Engagement, Response Time	Improved Student Interaction, Increased Satisfaction	Fragmented Communication, Low Engagement	Reflects need for engagement strategies in educational contexts	Sustainable Educational Outcomes, Higher Engagement	
	Educational Content Dissemination	Content Creation vs User Interaction	YouTube, Facebook, LinkedIn	Knowledge Dissemination, Content Reach	Knowledge Rates, Privacy Concerns	Low Engagement Rates, Privacy Concerns	Greater Knowledge Sharing, Higher Interaction	Limited Reach, Poor Engagement	Aligns with review's insights on content strategies for educational SMEs	Long-Term Knowledge Sharing, Improved

										Student Experience
Feedback Loops	Real-Time Feedback vs Data Privacy	Social Analytics, Feedback Platforms	Media Student Satisfaction, Privacy Compliance	Privacy Violations, Low Feedback Quality	Improved Communication, Greater Student Satisfaction	Difficulties in Managing Privacy Issues	Ties into review's emphasis on secure feedback systems			Long-Term Engagement, Trust, Privacy Compliance

6. Proposed Best Practices for Successful Study Topic Implementation

To maximize the competitive advantage that social media offers, SMEs must adhere to best practices that ensure scalable and effective organizational engagement. These best practices vary across industries, reflecting the specific needs, challenges, and strategic opportunities in each sector. In particular, industries such as retail, healthcare, finance, manufacturing, logistics, energy, and education require tailored approaches to social media implementation. Table 18 provides a comprehensive breakdown of the best practices, challenges, and strategic outcomes for each industry, tying these practices into the findings from the proposed systematic review. For example, in the retail sector, the personalization of customer experiences through targeted ads and influencer marketing is crucial for enhancing customer engagement and increasing sales. However, challenges such as content saturation and the management of customer data must be carefully navigated. Similarly, in healthcare, engaging patients through secure platforms like Facebook and LinkedIn, while ensuring compliance with data privacy regulations such as GDPR, can improve patient relationships and strengthen brand trust.

In finance, the use of AI-driven chatbots for real-time customer support helps SMEs to handle queries more efficiently, improving customer satisfaction while managing reputational risks. Meanwhile, in the manufacturing sector, leveraging LinkedIn and YouTube for thought leadership and operational updates can position a business as an industry leader, though consistent content creation remains a challenge. The logistics industry benefits from using AI-driven customer interaction tools, such as real-time delivery updates, while energy SMEs can use social media to promote sustainability initiatives, boosting public awareness and trust. Lastly, education SMEs should utilize platforms like YouTube for content delivery and Twitter for real-time engagement with students, addressing privacy concerns and fostering better communication.

Table 18. Proposed Best Practices for Successful Implementation of the Study.

Industry	Category	Subcategory	Best Practices	Challenges to Overcome	Strategic Outcomes	Ties into Proposed Systematic Review
Retail	Customer Engagement	Personalization & Sales	Use targeted ads, influencer marketing, and personalized recommendations to enhance customer experience.	Managing customer data, content saturation, and high competition	Increased sales, improved customer loyalty, enhanced brand awareness	Aligns with the systematic review's focus on personalized marketing and customer engagement as critical social media strategies for SMEs.
	Process Optimization	Workflow Management	Leverage AI-driven tools for managing inventory and automating sales processes.	Resistance to automation, high costs of implementation	Streamlined operations, reduced operational costs	Supports the review's findings on operational efficiency through digital tools.
	Branding	Influencer Partnerships	Collaborate with influencers and create user-generated content campaigns to boost brand visibility.	Privacy concerns, adapting content for diverse audiences	Greater brand awareness, stronger customer trust, and user engagement	Reflects the review's focus on strategic partnerships and branding through social media.
Healthcare	Patient Interaction	Secure Communication	Engage with patients via secure platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn) while ensuring compliance with health regulations.	Data privacy concerns, regulatory compliance (HIPAA, GDPR)	Improved patient relationships, enhanced trust, stronger brand reputation	Ties into the systematic review's examination of data privacy and regulatory challenges for SMEs using social media in sensitive industries.
	Educational Content	Patient Education	Use YouTube and Twitter to share health tips, tutorials, and updates on health awareness campaigns.	Content accuracy, maintaining engagement	Enhanced patient knowledge, greater outreach, and better brand reputation	Supports the review's exploration of content sharing for customer education and engagement.
	Feedback Management	Real-Time Feedback	Implement real-time feedback systems on social media for patient reviews and responses.	Managing negative feedback, ensuring responsiveness	Enhanced patient satisfaction, improved service delivery	Aligns with the review's focus on feedback management and real-time interaction for SMEs.
Finance	Customer Support	Real-Time Assistance	Use AI-driven chatbots on social media for instant customer queries and support.	Managing reputational risks, data security threats	Higher customer satisfaction, improved response times, compliance effectiveness	Connects with the review's discussion on using AI to enhance real-time customer support and manage reputation.

Manufacturing	Compliance Management	Data Privacy	Implement robust data protection measures on social media to comply with regulatory requirements.	High costs of compliance, evolving regulations	Building customer trust, avoiding penalties, and ensuring compliance	Directly ties to the review's analysis of regulatory and privacy challenges for SMEs.
	Branding	Reputation Management	Use social media monitoring tools to proactively manage brand reputation.	Misinformation, delayed responses	Strengthened brand trust, proactive issue management	Ties into the review's examination of reputation management strategies for SMEs.
	Thought Leadership	Operational Updates & Branding	Leverage LinkedIn and YouTube for thought leadership, sharing innovations, and process updates.	Creating relevant content consistently, limited social media engagement	Enhanced brand credibility, industry leadership, and operational visibility	Aligns with the review's discussion on branding and content creation strategies for increasing SME visibility.
	Customer Engagement	Real-Time Interaction	Use real-time social media tools to engage customers on product updates and inquiries.	Poor response times, managing customer expectations	Improved customer satisfaction, enhanced product visibility	Reflects the review's focus on real-time engagement tools for better customer interaction.
	Automation	Process Automation	Implement AI-driven automation for managing operations and workflows to reduce human error.	High implementation costs, resistance to change	Reduced operational costs, increased efficiency	Ties into the review's focus on operational efficiency and automation for SMEs.
Logistics	Customer Interaction	Delivery Updates	Use social media to provide real-time delivery updates, leveraging AI chatbots for customer queries.	Poor response time, managing real-time information effectively	Improved customer satisfaction, operational transparency, timely communication	Supports the review's findings on using real-time communication tools to improve operational transparency for SMEs.
	Process Optimization	Inventory Management	Use AI-driven automation for inventory tracking and logistics planning to ensure timely deliveries.	Resistance to automation, high implementation costs	Streamlined processes, reduced operational delays	Reflects the review's focus on process automation to enhance operational efficiency.
	Branding	Virtual Tours	Use virtual reality tools on social media platforms to showcase services or logistics infrastructure to potential clients.	High costs of creating virtual content, limited platform knowledge	Enhanced brand visibility, improved customer engagement through immersive experiences	Aligns with the review's discussion on leveraging advanced technologies for better customer engagement and brand growth.

Energy	Sustainability	Awareness & Advocacy	Share sustainability achievements and environmental goals on platforms like Twitter and LinkedIn.	Difficulty engaging non-environmentally conscious audiences	Stronger brand identity, greater customer trust, heightened public awareness	Ties into the review's exploration of how social media can be used to promote corporate social responsibility (CSR) in SMEs.
	Real-Time Interaction	Customer Feedback	Implement real-time customer feedback systems on social media to address queries related to sustainability initiatives.	Managing negative feedback, ensuring timely responses	Improved customer engagement, stronger sustainability advocacy	Connects with the review's focus on feedback management and real-time customer interaction.
	Branding	Green Marketing	Use social media platforms to promote green energy initiatives and educate customers on sustainability.	Engaging diverse audiences, adapting to trends in green marketing	Increased customer awareness, enhanced brand loyalty	Aligns with the review's analysis of branding and marketing strategies for SMEs, specifically in sustainability.
Education	Content Delivery	Student Engagement	Use YouTube for tutorials and Twitter for real-time class updates, AI tools for personalized learning.	Difficulty maintaining consistent engagement, data privacy concerns	Increased student engagement, improved learning experiences, better knowledge dissemination	Directly ties into the review's exploration of social media use for educational engagement and content sharing.
	Organizational Feedback	Staff & Student Interaction	Use social media platforms to collect feedback from students and staff for improved communication and curriculum adjustments.	Fragmented communication, managing privacy concerns	Improved staff-student communication, better feedback systems	Supports the review's analysis of feedback systems for improving organizational outcomes.
	Branding	Reputation & Visibility	Create a strong online presence for the educational institution using social media, leveraging influencer partnerships.	Privacy concerns, reputation management challenges	Enhanced brand visibility, improved student and stakeholder trust	Ties into the review's examination of branding and visibility through social media for educational SMEs.

7. Metrics and KPIs for Measuring Study Topic Performance

This section emphasizes the vital role that KPIs play in helping SMEs measure the effectiveness of their social media strategies. By breaking down performance metrics by industry, SMEs in sectors such as retail, healthcare, finance, manufacturing, and education can focus on tailored KPIs that address their specific goals—whether that be engagement rate, follower growth, or brand awareness. As outlined in Table 19, each KPI provides insights that help SMEs refine their approach to organizational engagement, overcome challenges, and seize opportunities for long-term growth.

These industry-specific insights help SMEs track their social media performance more accurately, enabling them to make data-driven decisions that align with both their short-term and long-term goals. The breakdown by industry allows for a nuanced approach that integrates the findings of this systematic review with practical strategies to drive business success across different sectors.

Table 19. Key Performance Indicators for Measuring Performance.

Industry	KPIs	Description	Contribution	Challenges to Overcome	Opportunities	How it ties to the Systematic Review
Retail	Engagement Rate	Measures interactions (likes, comments, shares) with retail content (e.g., product launches, promotions).	Helps retail SMEs understand how promotional content resonates with the audience, fostering deeper connections and driving sales.	Content fatigue, maintaining relevance in a crowded market	Improved sales and customer loyalty through interactive content	Helps retailers optimize customer engagement strategies for sales growth.
	Sales Conversion	Tracks the percentage of retail social media interactions that lead to purchases.	Directly links retail social media activity to revenue, helping understand which content drives sales.	Difficulty attributing sales to social media actions	Higher sales and repeat purchases through targeted campaigns	Supports conversion rate analysis tied to e-commerce performance.
	Brand Awareness	Assesses how well a retail brand is recognized and differentiated across platforms.	Helps retail SMEs measure market presence and distinguish themselves in highly competitive markets.	Competing for visibility with bigger brands	Greater brand visibility and customer recall through consistent messaging	Linked to strategies for increasing brand visibility in competitive environments.
Healthcare	Patient Engagement	Tracks how well healthcare SMEs interact with patients via secure platforms like Facebook and LinkedIn.	Helps measure how social content is engaging patients, improving relationships and trust.	Balancing patient confidentiality with public engagement	Improved patient care and reputation through personalized communication	Aligns with strategies for building trust and managing sensitive patient data.
	Follower Growth	Monitors increase in the number of followers for healthcare SMEs over time.	Reflects on how well healthcare SMEs are expanding their reach and attracting new patients through health education content.	Managing patient trust and privacy	Growth in patient base and public health awareness	Reflects strategies to expand health SME reach while safeguarding patient privacy.
	ROI	Assesses financial return on healthcare social media campaigns (e.g., educational posts, patient outreach).	Helps healthcare SMEs evaluate if their social media efforts are cost-effective and contributing to business sustainability.	Justifying social media investment in a regulated industry	Improved patient trust and return on healthcare investments	Ties to evaluating the cost-effectiveness of patient engagement efforts.

Finance	Customer Support	Measures the effectiveness of AI-driven chatbots in handling customer queries on platforms like LinkedIn.	Directly links social media activity to improved customer support and satisfaction for financial SMEs.	Managing reputational risks and response quality	Higher customer satisfaction and compliance through real-time support	Aligns with strategies to improve customer service and manage reputational risk.
	Compliance Rate	Tracks how well financial SMEs adhere to regulatory compliance requirements via social media platforms.	Ensures that social media strategies adhere to strict financial compliance regulations, fostering trust and avoiding legal challenges.	Navigating strict regulatory frameworks	Greater compliance effectiveness and reduced regulatory risks	Supports the need for compliance in digital financial services communication.
	Brand Awareness	Assesses the financial SME's visibility and brand reputation across social media platforms.	Helps financial SMEs measure how well they distinguish themselves in a highly regulated environment.	Regulatory constraints, and maintaining credibility	Enhanced reputation and long-term customer trust through transparency	Tied to increasing brand trust and visibility while ensuring regulatory compliance.
Manufacturing	Conversion Rate	Measures the proportion of social media interactions that result in product inquiries or orders.	Provides insight into how manufacturing SMEs convert social media engagement into direct business inquiries or sales conversions.	Managing product expectations and delivery timelines	Higher sales conversions and product interest from online campaigns	Tied to improving the efficiency of sales conversions through social media.
	Market Reach	Tracks the potential number of unique users who have seen product updates or manufacturing processes.	Helps manufacturing SMEs assess visibility and customer interest in their operations and product innovations.	Navigating niche markets and customer acquisition	Improved operational visibility and greater product demand	Aligns with strategies for broadening the reach and visibility of manufacturing SMEs.
	Thought Leadership	Tracks engagement with thought leadership content (e.g., process updates, innovations) via LinkedIn.	Helps manufacturing SMEs measure how well they position themselves as industry leaders through social media.	Maintaining content relevance and thought leadership	Enhanced industry credibility and competitive differentiation	Supports positioning SMEs as thought leaders in the manufacturing industry.
Education	Student Engagement	Measures how well social media platforms like YouTube and Twitter are engaging students.	Helps education SMEs assess how their content (e.g., tutorials, class updates) connects with students and drives learning.	Managing consistent engagement with diverse students	Increased student interaction and improved learning outcomes	Tied to optimizing student engagement and learning outcomes through social media.

Follower Growth	Tracks the increase in the number of followers for educational content across social platforms.	Reflects the reach of educational SMEs, helping them understand how well they attract and retain students through social media.	Maintaining engagement platforms	follower across	Improved student retention and broader dissemination of learning materials	Aligned with strategies for expanding the reach of educational content.
Content Reach	Assesses how far educational materials (e.g., tutorials, webinars) are distributed across platforms.	Helps education SMEs gauge the effectiveness of content distribution and audience interaction with learning materials.	Overcoming saturation competition	content and	Broader reach of educational resources and enhanced learning engagement	Reflects strategies for enhancing knowledge dissemination through social media.

8. Real Case Studies and How They Relate to Proposed Systematic Review

Some of the conclusions made in the systematic reviews are going to be confirmed and jilted by actual case studies. Real-world examples might offer a valuable understanding of how companies of different sizes, sectors, and locales have reacted to digital technologies such as blockchain, artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, and the Internet of Things. This might be a study of a small manufacturing company that improved its supply chain by implementing an IoT system, it illustrates the advantages and difficulties of doing so. From the point of view of the business, efficiency may have increased, but this could also lead to increased expenses and even resistance from the workforce. As a result, the researcher has the chance to figure out how IoT impacts operational efficiency, which was one of the factors found in the systematic review. Also, the case studies that focus on retail may show how SMEs have used e-commerce platforms and digital marketing to expand their markets. The researcher will be able to determine whether the important factors such as consumer engagement and resource limitations correspond to what firms actually face by comparing these real-world outcomes with the results of systematic reviews. During this process, case studies like this one may at times reveal advantages or problems in areas like cybersecurity and digital infrastructure maintenance that were missed during the initial scan.

The second area includes real case studies that mostly bridge the gaps created by the examination of systematic reviews. This will lead to a better knowledge of the specific contextual contexts that SMEs encounter and the corresponding particular challenges associated with their use of digital technology. A case study of a healthcare SME in a developing nation, for instance, may highlight problems like integrating new technology with antiquated processes and being aware of the privacy laws that apply to patient data. The particular findings may add to the systematic review's conclusions by explaining how theoretical difficulties function in a real-world business setting in light of these particular instances. Putting another way, actual case study experiences add context to the broad conclusions that result from systematic assessments and offer light on the ways in which digital technologies impact small and medium-sized businesses. They enable the establishment of policies and procedures that will support SMEs in overcoming obstacles and maximizing the advantages of digital transformation. Case studies help close the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application by providing insightful information on particular obstacles that need to be addressed. This results in more comprehensive and useful conclusions.

Table 21. Real case studies and their correlation to the Study.

Ref.	Aspect	Case Study	Opportunities	Challenges	Insights for SMEs
[107]	Reaching New Customers	Gymshark (UK)	Leveraged Instagram and YouTube influencers to reach a global audience and expand quickly with minimal ad spend.	Managing relationships with influencers and sustaining long-term engagement in a competitive space.	Social media platforms can serve as powerful tools for global brand expansion, even with limited budgets.
[108]	Building Customer Loyalty	Sweetgreen (USA)	Used social media (Twitter, Instagram) to engage directly with customers, gather real-time feedback, and improve services.	Time-intensive process of responding to customers and managing social media interactions regularly.	Direct engagement with customers on social media can boost loyalty and provide valuable insights for improvement.
[109]	Cost-Effective Marketing	Dollar Shave Club (USA)	Created a viral YouTube video that led to rapid growth and brand recognition with minimal marketing expenses.	Viral content is unpredictable, and the brand must continue delivering engaging content post-viral success.	Creative content on social media can be a low-cost marketing tool for SMEs looking for wide exposure.
[110]	Enhancing Brand Image	Lush Cosmetics (UK)	Built a strong brand community on Instagram by encouraging user-generated content and	Facing a backlash if company values are perceived as	Leveraging social media to showcase brand values can attract loyal

			promoting ethical products.	inconsistent with customer expectations.	customers, especially in niche markets.
[111]	Managing Customer Complaints	Domino's Pizza (USA)	Addressed customer complaints via Twitter, using the platform to improve service quality and recover brand reputation.	Quick spread of negative feedback can harm brand image if not managed properly.	SMEs need to actively monitor and manage social media interactions to address issues before they escalate.
[112]	Driving Sales	MVMT Watches (USA)	Grew sales through Instagram by focusing on influencer partnerships and targeting millennial consumers.	Balancing influencer marketing budgets and ensuring authenticity in partnerships.	Social media offers a way to drive sales through targeted, influencer-based campaigns for specific audiences.
[113]	Expanding Market Reach	Oatly (Sweden)	Capitalized on social media trends to promote plant-based products and reach health-conscious consumers.	Risk of alienating traditional dairy consumers and backlash from industry competitors.	Engaging with trending topics on social media can help SMEs tap into new markets and consumer preferences.
[114]	Enhancing Customer Engagement	Patagonia (USA)	Used storytelling on Instagram to connect with environmentally conscious consumers and build brand loyalty.	Maintaining authenticity while addressing complex environmental issues can be challenging.	Storytelling can create a strong emotional connection with customers, fostering loyalty and advocacy.
[115]	Innovating Product Offerings	Warby Parker (USA)	Employed social media for direct-to-consumer sales, enabling innovative eyewear solutions at lower prices.	The online fitting process may deter some customers who prefer in-person shopping experiences.	Utilizing social media to innovate and market new products can enhance competitiveness in traditional markets.
[116]	Improving Customer Service	Zappos (USA)	Leveraged social media to provide responsive customer service and enhance overall customer satisfaction.	High expectations from customers can lead to challenges in consistently meeting service demands.	Proactive social media customer service can significantly boost brand reputation and customer loyalty.
[117]	Creating Brand Awareness	Nike (USA)	Launched social media campaigns that resonate with social justice movements, increasing brand visibility.	Potential backlash if the campaign message is perceived as insincere or exploitative.	Aligning brand messaging with social movements can elevate brand awareness and customer support among target audiences.
[118]	Driving Community Engagement	LEGO (Denmark)	Fostered a community of creators on social media by encouraging user-generated content and collaboration.	Balancing community expectations with corporate goals can be difficult.	Building a community around products can enhance customer engagement and foster brand loyalty over time.

Table 21 above presents real-world case studies of SMEs using digital technologies, including e-commerce, AI, and IoT. In order to clarify the industries to which these kinds of technology are being applied, cases are categorized by industry. Important findings highlighted the advantages that businesses experienced, such as increased productivity or market expansion, but they also shed light on the difficulties that these situations presented, like increased expenses and employee resistance. By highlighting the differences between theoretical predictions and actual results, the case studies, in turn, offer even more insight into the practical ramifications of the digital transition. For example, while systematic assessments have shown that IoT adoption leads to increased operational efficiency, certain case studies have found that such integration may come at a significant cost and encounter opposition from workers. This practical view helps in the researchers' identification of gaps in the body of literature, allowing them to communicate the conclusion more subtly while taking into account the unique difficulties faced by SMEs across a range of industries. In general, the real-world examples included here contribute to the conversation around digital technology adoption and assist SMEs in various ways as they successfully navigate their individual digital journeys.

10. Proposed Roadmap for SMEs Businesses and Policy Recommendations

Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) play a vital role in driving economic growth across multiple industries, but their long-term sustainability largely depends on their ability to integrate emerging digital technologies. This section outlines a structured roadmap designed to assist SMEs in navigating digital transformation, offering actionable insights into strategic planning, workforce training, technology integration, and global expansion. By adopting industry-specific strategies, SMEs can enhance customer engagement, improve operational efficiency, and expand their market reach. As shown in Table 22, the roadmap is tailored to the unique needs of industries such as retail, healthcare, logistics, and manufacturing, breaking down each phase of digital transformation—from setting strategic goals to scaling operations for global competitiveness. In retail, for example, the focus is on omnichannel strategies and enhancing customer interactions through targeted advertisements and e-commerce platforms. In contrast, healthcare SMEs can improve patient care by adopting IoT and AI for personalized treatments, while logistics companies can optimize their supply chains using blockchain and AI-driven automation.

Using proposed roadmap, SMEs can not only achieve digital maturity but also position themselves to compete in a global marketplace. The table further outlines key policy recommendations, such as providing grants, training incentives, and regulatory support, to ensure the smooth integration of digital technologies into SME operations. Each stage of this roadmap is designed to ensure that SMEs are fully equipped to harness the benefits of digital transformation, thus ensuring long-term growth and competitiveness.

Table 22. Proposed Roadmap for SMEs businesses and Policy Recommendations.

Stage	Industry	Category	Subcategories	Key Actions for SMEs	Policy Recommendations	Expected Outcomes	Challenges	Opportunities	Ties into Proposed Systematic Review
Stage 1: Goal Setting	Retail	Strategic Planning	- E-commerce	- Set customer-centric goals	- Support omnichannel adoption	Improved customer experience and sales growth	Managing multiple channels and inventory	Seamless customer experience and increased sales	Aligns with enhanced customer engagement through social media.
			- Customer Engagement	- Plan omnichannel strategies	- Tax incentives for e-commerce				
	Healthcare	Strategic Planning	- Patient Care	- Define goals for patient satisfaction	- Provide digital health regulations	Improved patient care and operational efficiency	Adherence to healthcare regulations	Personalized care and remote monitoring	Supports healthcare digital transformation for engagement strategies.
			- Digital Health	- Plan for IoT adoption	- Offer funding for IoT devices				
Logistics	Supply Chain Optimization	- AI for Automation	- Establish transparent supply chains	- Support blockchain adoption	Increased operational efficiency and transparency	Difficulty in adopting new tech for small players	Enhanced supply chain transparency and automation	Links to supply chain transparency and customer engagement.	
		- Blockchain	- Automate tracking systems	- Provide AI incentives					
Manufacturing	Smart Manufacturing	- AI-driven Processes	- Set productivity goals	- Provide grants for adopting smart manufacturing tech	Reduced production costs and increased productivity	High cost of smart manufacturing technologies	Efficiency in production and reduced downtime	Relates to process optimization and customer-driven manufacturing.	
		- IoT	- Implement IoT in real-time monitoring						

Stage 2: Training	Retail	Workforce Development	- Digital Skills - E-commerce Tools	- Train employees in omnichannel tools - Upgrade skills for analytics	- Provide incentives for e-commerce training - Support employee development	Enhanced workforce efficiency in digital sales and customer interaction	Limited digital skills among employees	Higher engagement and better use of social media tools	Connects with the best practices for social media transformation.
	Healthcare	Workforce Development	- Patient Interaction Tools - IoT	- Train staff on IoT devices - Educate on secure communication	- Support digital health education - Ensure compliance training	Improved patient interaction and secure communication	Resistance to digital adoption in health	Real-time, secure patient monitoring	Enhances patient communication and data security through digital tools.
	Logistics	Workforce Digital Training	- AI Tools - Supply Chain Tracking	- Educate workforce on AI-driven supply chain management	- Support AI training programs for logistics - Provide tax benefits	Streamlined logistics and improved real-time tracking	Difficulty in training older workforce	Enhanced supply chain optimization and customer satisfaction	Supports logistics transparency and engagement improvements.
Stage 3: Technology Integration	Manufacturing	Workforce Development	- AI Processes - IoT Integration	- Train in AI-driven production processes - Upskill in IoT usage	- Support training in smart manufacturing - Provide incentives	Improved production workflows and higher operational accuracy	High cost of specialized training	Boost in efficiency and streamlined production processes	Relates to production efficiency and AI integration.
	Retail	Customer Engagement	- E-commerce - Social Media Tools	- Integrate e-commerce with social platforms	- Provide grants for e-commerce expansion	Seamless online and offline	Managing multi-channel	Expanded market reach	Connects to customer-centric engagement

				- Use influencer marketing	- Support digital transformation	engagement, higher sales	sales and engagement	through personalization	strategies via social platforms.
	Healthcare	IoT Integration in Health	- AI-driven Care - IoT Monitoring	- Integrate IoT for patient monitoring	- Provide grants for IoT in healthcare	Improved patient monitoring and diagnostics accuracy	Complexity in maintaining IoT devices and managing patient data	Personalized healthcare and reduced operational costs	Supports digital health engagement and customer interaction.
	Logistics	Supply Chain Automation	- AI Automation - Blockchain	- Implement AI for logistics - Automate supply chain with blockchain	- Provide grants for logistics automation - Support blockchain adoption	Improved transparency and reduced delays	High costs and complexity in blockchain adoption	Enhanced supply chain management and customer transparency	Ties into logistics optimization through social media channels.
	Manufacturing	Smart Factory Setup	- IoT Monitoring - AI Optimization	- Implement real-time IoT monitoring - Optimize production with AI	- Provide grants for smart manufacturing technology	Increased production efficiency and real-time monitoring	High cost and complexity of AI integration	Enhanced production process, reduced downtime	Relates to smart production using real-time IoT and AI.
Stage 4: Monitoring & Evaluation	Retail	Performance Tracking	- Social Media Metrics - Sales Conversion	- Track sales, engagement, and reach metrics - Adjust based on data	- Provide tools for social media analytics - Support performance tracking tools	Improved campaign performance and sales growth	Difficulty in accurately tracking multiple KPIs	Improved targeting and better sales conversion	Links to social media performance tracking for customer engagement.

Stage 5: Global Competitiveness	Healthcare	Digital Metrics Tracking	- Patient Feedback - Data Analytics	- Use patient feedback tools - Track IoT data for care improvement	- Support patient data analytics - Provide tools for feedback collection	Enhanced patient satisfaction and real-time care adjustments	Privacy concerns and data management challenges	Improved patient care and operational efficiency	Supports healthcare engagement through data-driven approaches.
	Logistics	AI Supply Chain Monitoring	- Real-time Tracking - Blockchain	- Monitor supply chain in real-time - Use blockchain for transparency	- Provide tools for blockchain monitoring - Support AI logistics tracking	Streamlined operations and transparency	Difficulties in blockchain and real-time AI management	Improved logistics transparency and customer satisfaction	Ties into logistics optimization through supply chain management.
	Manufacturing	IoT and AI Monitoring	- Real-time Production Data - AI Adjustments	- Monitor real-time production data - Use AI for predictive maintenance	- Provide grants for smart factory tools - Support AI monitoring	Improved productivity and predictive maintenance	High cost of real-time data monitoring and AI integration	Streamlined production and reduced equipment failures	Relates to smart manufacturing with real-time monitoring.
	Retail	Scaling & Market Expansion	- Digital Growth - Global Reach	- Scale digital tools globally - Expand market reach through social platforms	- Provide export incentives - Regulatory support for global expansion	Increased global competitiveness and market reach	Challenges in adapting to international markets	Access to global markets through digital transformation	Supports global digital strategy for customer engagement.
	Healthcare	Global Expansion	- International Collaboration - Digital Healthcare	- Implement digital health tools globally - Foster international collaboration	- Provide export incentives - Support for digital healthcare expansion	Improved global healthcare operations and patient outcomes	Regulatory differences across regions	Enhanced global presence in healthcare technology	Connects to global healthcare expansion with digital tools.

Logistics	Scaling & Expansion	- Global Supply Chain Transparency	- Expand supply chain operations globally - Use blockchain for global transparency	- Provide export incentives - Support global logistics scalability	Improved global supply chain transparency and efficiency	High cost of global supply chain optimization	Enhanced global supply chain integration	Ties into global supply chain optimization through blockchain.
Manufacturing	Scaling & Automation	- Smart Manufacturing Growth - Global Market Expansion	- Scale AI-driven processes globally - Integrate smart manufacturing in global operations	- Provide export incentives - Regulatory support for global expansion	Enhanced global productivity and competitiveness	Difficulty in adapting manufacturing processes globally	Access to global markets through smart manufacturing	Relates to global expansion through AI and IoT.

11. Discussion

This systematic literature review explored the challenges and opportunities of social media for organizational engagement in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). The study identified key dimensions related to social media use, including enhanced customer interaction, improved brand visibility, market reach, and the management of negative feedback, privacy concerns, and resource allocation. The analysis confirms that effective social media strategies can significantly enhance SMEs' engagement with their audience, ultimately leading to improved organizational performance and growth. The following sections discuss the study's findings in relation to the initial research questions and their practical implications.

RQ1: How can organizations use social media strategies to specifically enhance brand loyalty among existing customers?

This review demonstrates that organizations can significantly increase brand loyalty by leveraging tailored content and actively engaging with customers on social media. Businesses that personalize their interactions, such as sharing user-generated content, showcasing customer success stories, and giving behind-the-scenes access, foster a stronger emotional connection with their audience. Additionally, providing exclusive benefits to loyal customers, such as special promotions or early access to products, creates a sense of exclusivity that encourages continued engagement. The systematic review suggests that consistent engagement, timely responses to customer feedback, and community-building strategies lead to increased trust, deeper emotional bonds, and higher retention rates.

RQ2: What strategies are most effective for organizations in mitigating the impact of negative feedback on social media?

The review highlights the importance of timely and transparent communication in managing negative feedback. When organizations address complaints promptly and professionally, they can prevent negative situations from escalating. Offering solutions through direct or public responses demonstrates that the company values its customers and is willing to address their concerns. Moreover, turning negative experiences into positive ones by offering compensation or improved services can help regain customer trust. The systematic review found that businesses actively monitoring social media for negative feedback, and addressing it in real-time, are better equipped to safeguard their reputation and customer satisfaction.

RQ3: How do privacy concerns influence customer trust and engagement on social media platforms?

The findings indicate that privacy concerns are a significant factor influencing customer trust and engagement. The systematic review shows that customers are increasingly cautious about sharing personal data online, given the rise in data breaches and misuse of information. SMEs that emphasize transparency regarding data usage, clearly communicate privacy policies, and offer robust data security measures build stronger relationships with their customers. In contrast, failure to address privacy issues results in a loss of trust and diminished engagement. Therefore, businesses must prioritize data security and make privacy protection an integral part of their social media strategy to maintain customer loyalty and active participation.

RQ4: How have recent algorithm changes on social media platforms affected organic reach and engagement strategies for organizations?

Algorithm changes on platforms like Facebook and Instagram have decreased organic reach for business content, pushing organizations to adopt more engaging, shareable content to maintain visibility. The systematic review reveals that companies must focus on creating high-quality, visually appealing content that drives interaction, such as polls, quizzes, and live videos. The shift towards paid promotions and ads is also evident, with many SMEs investing more in paid campaigns to counterbalance the reduced organic reach. The review suggests that organizations need to balance innovative content strategies with targeted paid campaigns to maximize engagement despite the algorithmic constraints.

RQ5: What key performance indicators (KPIs) are most reliable for measuring the return on investment (ROI) of social media engagement in SMEs?

The study found that engagement metrics such as likes, shares, comments, and direct messages are valuable indicators of audience interaction. Conversion rates, sales, and follower growth are crucial KPIs for determining the business impact of social media efforts. Additionally, tracking brand sentiment and customer satisfaction through sentiment analysis offers deeper insights into public perceptions of the brand. The systematic review emphasizes that combining engagement and financial metrics (e.g., revenue generated from social media campaigns) allows SMEs to accurately measure ROI and optimize their social media strategies accordingly.

12. Conclusions

This systematic review, which analyzed 104 studies over the past decade, uncovers both the significant opportunities and inherent challenges of social media engagement for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Social media platforms offer SMEs a powerful means to enhance brand loyalty by enabling personalized interactions, fostering community-building strategies, and delivering consistent, targeted content. These approaches allow organizations to deepen relationships with their customers, creating a foundation for sustained loyalty and engagement. However, the review also highlights that effectively addressing negative feedback is essential to maintaining a positive brand image. SMEs that respond promptly and transparently to criticism can mitigate the reputational risks associated with adverse online comments, reinforcing trust and demonstrating accountability. Privacy concerns emerged as a critical factor in influencing customer trust and engagement. In an era of increasing data security awareness, customers are more likely to engage with organizations that prioritize robust data protection measures and clearly communicate their privacy policies. SMEs that are transparent about their data practices and committed to safeguarding customer information will gain a competitive advantage by fostering trust.

Recent changes to algorithms on platforms like Facebook and Instagram have reduced the organic reach of SME content, compelling organizations to adapt their strategies. To stay visible and maintain engagement, SMEs must focus on optimizing their content for shareability, investing in paid promotions, and creating high-quality, interactive posts that resonate with their target audiences. Key performance indicators (KPIs), such as engagement metrics (likes, shares, comments), conversion rates, customer retention, and overall brand sentiment, play a crucial role in assessing the return on investment (ROI) of social media initiatives. These metrics allow SMEs to gauge the effectiveness of their social media strategies, make data-driven decisions, and refine their approach to drive better business outcomes.

Looking ahead, future research should aim to develop more advanced tools for measuring the long-term impact of social media on SME sustainability and growth. Additionally, policymakers and business leaders must work together to provide SMEs with the necessary resources, training, and digital infrastructure to fully capitalize on the benefits of social media in an increasingly competitive and evolving digital landscape. By doing so, SMEs will be better positioned to leverage social media as a tool for enhancing customer engagement, building brand equity, and ensuring long-term success in the digital age.

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